

Turnkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

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Implementation of the FWCR software platform

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GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CAPS	Common Acquisition Protocol Server
CIS	Critical Infrastructure System
CLR	Common Language Runtime
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma-separated values
DB	Database
DBA	Database-Administrator
DYFI	Did You Feel It
EEW	Earthquake Early Warning
EF	Essential Facility

EMS-98	European Macroseismic Scale Intensity
ESHM13	European Seismic Hazard Model 2013
ESHM20	European Seismic Hazard Model 2020
ETAS	Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequence
FDSNWS	International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks Web Service
FWCR	Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction – Response
GB	General Building
GDAL	Geospatial Data Abstraction Library
GMICE	Ground Motion to Intensity Conversion Equation
GMM	Ground-Motion Models
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IIS	Internet Information Services
IM	Intensity Measure
MMI	Modified Mercalli Intensity Scale
OEF	Operational Earthquake Forecasting
PGA	Peak Ground Acceleration
PHP	Hypertext Preprocessor
REST	Representational State Transfer
RRE	Rapid Response to Earthquake
RS4D	RaspberryShake 4D
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SVN	Apache Subversion
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VM	Virtual Machine
WMS	Web Map Service

INDEX OF CONTENTS

Document revision history	ii
List of partners.....	ii
Glossary.....	ii
Index of Contents	iv
Index of Figures.....	vii
Index of Tables.....	ix
1 Introduction	10
2 Platform general concept and functionalities	10
2.1 Real-time data transmission/acquisition.....	12
2.2 Scientific engines and processing.....	14
2.2.1 Event Listener engine.....	14
2.2.2 EEW engine.....	15
2.2.3 RRE engine.....	16
2.2.4 OEF engine.....	16
2.2.5 Processing engine infrastructural components	17
2.2.5.1 Database	17
2.2.5.2 REST API Server.....	18
2.2.5.3 GeoServer.....	18
2.2.5.4 Notification server.....	18
2.3 Outputs and Communication.....	19
2.3.1 EEW	19
2.3.2 RRE	19
2.3.3 OEF (aftershock).....	20
2.3.4 Event simulation.....	20
3 Platform Installation	21
3.1 Instrumentation Setup and Real-time Data Transmission/Acquisition.....	21
3.2 EEW, RRE, and OEF Engines Setup	21
3.2.1 Prerequisites	21
3.2.2 Engine docker images.....	21
3.2.3 Installing data for engine	21
3.2.3.1 Setting up the environment.....	22
3.2.3.2 Create database.....	22
3.2.3.3 Initialize database	22
3.2.3.4 Install static data.....	22
3.2.3.5 Install site-specific data	23

3.2.4	Running the installer script.....	35
3.2.5	Running the engine for the installed data	36
3.2.5.1	Launching GeoServer	36
3.2.5.2	Launching engine components	37
3.3	Cloud-based Graphical User Interface Setup	41
3.3.1	Prerequisites	41
3.3.1.1	VM1	41
3.3.1.2	VM2.....	42
3.3.2	Installation VM1	42
3.3.2.1	TURNkey Management component.....	43
3.3.2.2	TURNkey scientific engine - service API	43
3.3.2.3	TURNkey - Event creation service API	43
3.3.2.4	TURNkey Alert service API.....	44
3.3.2.5	Mobile APP service API 1.....	44
3.3.2.6	Mobile App service API 2	44
3.3.2.7	Wrapper component	44
3.3.2.8	Notify Service component	44
3.3.3	Installation VM2.....	45
3.3.3.1	Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP).....	45
3.3.3.2	Apache.....	46
3.3.3.3	Node.js.....	46
3.3.3.4	Postgres component.....	46
3.3.3.5	Geoviewer.....	47
3.3.4	Installation of the TURNkey Database SQL Server.....	49
3.3.5	Configuration.....	49
3.3.5.1	TURNkey Management component.....	49
3.3.5.2	Wrapper Geos.....	51
3.3.5.3	Notify Service – Configuration	51
3.3.5.4	Geoviewer – Configuration	51
3.3.5.5	Configuration checklist.....	55
4	Platform up-running: Synthetic Icelandopolis.....	57
4.1	General characteristics of the Iceland testbed	57
4.2	Platform installation and setting up.....	57
4.2.1	Configuration and setting up of the local seismic networks.....	58
4.2.2	Real-time seismic data transmission from networks to the platform.....	58
4.2.3	Setup of the scientific engines	58
4.2.3.1	Parameters	58

4.2.3.2	Hazard data	58
4.2.3.3	Exposure data	59
4.2.3.4	Vulnerability data	61
4.3	Real-time simulation.....	61
4.3.1	EEW	61
4.3.2	RRE	64
4.3.3	OEF.....	72
4.4	Event simulation.....	73
5	References	74

INDEX OF FIGURES

Figure 1. The general concept of the TURNkey FWCR platform	10
Figure 2. TURNkey system components.....	11
Figure 3. Screenshot of the station view of the TURNkey platform in Europe. On the left side, the real-time stream of station R7971 located in the middle of France is shown. The colours of the triangles represent the recent ground motion, the red triangles indicate seismic triggers from the automatic processing	13
Figure 4. Study area, shake map area, and background seismicity area.....	13
Figure 5. Illustration of the chronological sequence of Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF), Earthquake Early Warning (EEW), and Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE) and simulation.....	14
Figure 6. Event listener engine.....	15
Figure 7. The EEW engine.....	15
Figure 8. The RRE engine.....	16
Figure 9. The OEF engine.....	17
Figure 10. The PostgreSQL database.....	17
Figure 11. The REST API server.....	18
Figure 12. The GeoServer.....	18
Figure 13. The notification server.....	18
Figure 14 IIS installation options.....	42
Figure 15 Compilation of the API module.....	48
Figure 16 Parameters for the installation of Nodejs.....	49
Figure 17 Check configuration.....	54
Figure 18 Personalisation of the menu display label.....	55
Figure 19. Iceland seismic zonation maps from UIce.....	59
Figure 20. The synthetic V_{S30} map for the Icelandopolis region.....	60
Figure 21. Synthetic Icelandopolis exposure data: geoareas: black line; general buildings: orange circle; CISs: blue diamond; EFs: red cross.....	60
Figure 22 Left: the EEW alert on the platform. Right: the EEW alert for aftershock in the mobile application.	61
Figure 23. The most affected region covering the area with estimated $PGA \geq$ pre-defined threshold in %g.	62
Figure 24. The PGA shake map in g. The synthetic case study is for demonstration only. The high ground shaking estimates are due to high GMM estimates for soil sites.....	62
Figure 25. The EMS-98 intensity shake map. The synthetic case study is for demonstration only. The high ground shaking estimates are due to high GMM estimates for soil sites.	63
Figure 26. Communication between the GUI and end-user.	63
Figure 27. Communication between the GUI and the public.	64
Figure 28. Threshold-based risk-mitigation measures automatically triggered.	64
Figure 29. Four instrumental PGA (circle sized by PGA values in %g) are used to update the shake map. The epicentre of the mainshock is denoted by the star.	65
Figure 30. The updated PGA shake map in g. The high ground shaking estimates are due to 1) high GMM estimates for soil sites; 2) synthetic observations; 3) strong spatial correlation.....	66
Figure 31. The updated EMS-98 intensity shake map. The high ground shaking estimates are due to 1) high GMM estimates for soil sites; 2) synthetic observations; 3) strong spatial correlation.....	66
Figure 32. The map of average damage estimates for general buildings / geoarea.....	67
Figure 33. The general risk and loss estimation table for general buildings / geoarea.....	67
Figure 34. The detailed risk and loss estimation results for general buildings / geoarea.....	68
Figure 35 The map view of EFs and CISs risk and loss results. There is no damage to “the FUTURE airport control tower”.....	68
Figure 36 The general risk and loss estimation table for Efs and CISs.....	69
Figure 37. The detailed risk and loss estimation results for EFs and CISs.....	69
Figure 38. Submit eyewitness report on the TURNkey platform.....	70

Figure 39. Submit eyewitness report on the TURNkey app	70
Figure 40. The updated map of average damage estimates for general buildings / geoarea	71
Figure 41. The updated map view of EFs and CISs risk and loss results. The “FUTURE high school” is observed to be partially damaged.	71
Figure 42. The event catalogue between 2021-02-24 00:00:00 and 2021-02-25 00:00:00 observed by the TURNkey instrumental network	72
Figure 43. The OEF seismic hazard results given a strong mainshock-aftershock sequence (in Figure 42) ..	72
Figure 44. The OEF seismic hazard results given a weak mainshock-aftershock sequence.	73
Figure 45. Event simulation	73
Figure 46. The distribution of the vulnerability levels in geoareas.	74

INDEX OF TABLES

Table 1. List of OEF parameters	25
Table 2. Seismicity info parameters	27
Table 3. Risk parameters	27
Table 4. Shake map parameters	28
Table 5. Site classification.....	29
Table 6. Topography parameter description.....	31
Table 7. Exposure data	31
Table 8 The interface path for system setting. The user writes in step 3 the parameters to be changed.....	50
Table 9 Parameters to be configured	51
Table 10 The necessary records for agency_code and customer_code	53
Table 11 Cloud-based graphical user interface installation checklist.....	56

1 INTRODUCTION

The TURNkey FWCR (Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction – Response) platform is a multi-sensor-based earthquake information system, facilitating earthquake forecasting and enabling early warning and rapid response actions. The FWCR platform has been designed to be based on low-cost multi-sensor units and a cloud-based computer system, which can be distributed as a fully operational TURNkey product to public authorities/decision-makers (e.g., disaster management authorities, political authorities), first responders (e.g., civil protection, search-and-rescue teams, emergency medical services) and private companies (including operators of critical infrastructure) and general businesses (including the insurance industry). The overall concept of the TURNkey platform is shown in Figure 1. This platform can assist the identified stakeholders to react at the earliest stage to earthquakes, to reduce the direct and indirect (follow-up) impacts and consequences.

Figure 1. The general concept of the TURNkey FWCR platform

The present document describes the general concept and the functionalities of the platform and specifies its installation of the instruments, scientific engine, and the cloud-based graphical interface. Moreover, a demonstration for a hypothetical site of interest is included to show the available functionalities and the platform's potential impact on earthquake disaster management.

2 PLATFORM GENERAL CONCEPT AND FUNCTIONALITIES

The TURNkey platform is composed of three main components: the instrument network managed by GMP, the cloud-based graphical user interface developed by B80, and the scientific engine developed by NORSAR, as shown in Figure 2.

The instrument network collects and processes seismic data through the seismic monitoring platform SeisComP. The resultant dynamic input data (i.e., the event location and magnitude, instrumental recordings, felt report, and Radon data) are then sent to the scientific engine on request through three application programming interfaces (APIs): (1) the International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks web service (FDSNWS) for inventory data; (2) QuakeLink for the dynamic event data, including location, magnitude the corresponding peak intensity measure, e.g., peak ground acceleration (PGA), instrument arrival data, and Did-You-Feel-It (DYFI) felt reports; and (3) common acquisition protocol server (CAPS) for seismic instrumental recordings, e.g., PGA, and non-seismic instrument recordings, e.g., radon data.

Figure 2. TURNkey system components

The graphical user interface (GUI) facilitates and evaluates risk management in real-time and for various risk scenarios. On one hand, the GUI visualizes the results sent by the scientific engine at both regional (i.e., map) and local (e.g., building-specific information) levels and constantly refreshes the visualizations if results are updated. On the other hand, the GUI helps communications within and across different organizations/responders that have access to the platform service through the emergency protocols defined during the platform configuration. Moreover, through the TURNkey app, the engine can access the damage observations uploaded by the first responders in the field.

The scientific engine is composed of various internal processes, such as the earthquake early warning (EEW) process, the rapid response to earthquake (RRE) process, the operational earthquake forecasting (OEF) process, and the event listener process. These processes can be triggered to perform the desired analysis and the mutual communication (e.g., notify, read and write) between these processes and the TURNkey database (DB). Moreover, the scientific engine interacts with three external web APIs. The GUI can send a request to the internal API server to access the database and send a web map service (WMS) request to the GeoServer to obtain the map-type results. The QuakeLink API can send the information about the detected event to the scientific engine automatically and it can also send the instrumental recording, DYFI data, and event catalogue on request. The CAPS API can send the radon data on request.

As shown in Figure 2, the instrument network continuously monitors the area of interest. When an earthquake occurs, the instrument network collects the seismic signals and sends them to the SeisComP event process to evaluate the event magnitude, intensity and location and compute the ground-motion intensity measures (e.g., PGA). This information is sent to the scientific engine through the QuakeLink API automatically. The event listener process will report the earthquake to the TURNkey DB if the event occurs within the study area (i.e., a large area covering the instrument network) and its magnitude is strong enough to cause potentially damage, which triggers the EEW process. The EEW process computes the expected ground motions in the area of interest (also defined as the shake map area). If the ground shaking (e.g., in terms of PGA) is above a certain threshold (either defined by the user or estimated from the hazard map), the EEW process first produces a warning and computes the most affected area buffer, which is sent to the GUI, and then launches the RRE and OEF processes. Once triggered, the RRE quickly computes an early estimate of the shake

map based on the magnitude and ground-motion models (GMMs). The base shake map is later updated using instrument recordings and/or DYFI reports obtained via the QuakeLink API. The estimated results are updated to the DB and the maps are sent to the GeoServer. When the results are generated, a notification is sent to GUI. The OEF process computes the probability of exceedance of a certain PGA level using both the background seismicity data (e.g., seismic zonation map and seismicity rate) and the short-term seismic and/or non-seismic data (e.g., aftershock sequences and radon data). Moreover, the OEF process presents an increased probability of exceeding the PGA level, which can be used as a certain threshold to trigger alarms depending on the users' preference. The OEF hazard results will communicate with the DB and the GeoServer. The Notification server notifies the GUI when new information is available, and the representational state transfer (REST) server processes the requests from the GUI. Finally, the results computed from the scientific engine will be made available for the GUI through the REST server, notification server, and GeoServer. The user can visualize the real-time impact of the earthquake, disseminate information and coordinate the emergency responses through the GUI. Furthermore, the TURNkey system can also run earthquake scenarios to facilitate disaster planning.

2.1 Real-time data transmission/acquisition

The real-time data utilized in the TURNkey system includes the data collected from the multi-sensor unit (i.e., conventional sensors and smartphones) and the TURNkey platform and app.

The multi-conventional sensor unit is based on the RaspberryShake 4D (RS4D), a low-cost sensor with 3 strong-motion components (Z|N|E) and a vertical weak-motion component. Within the development of the TURNkey project, the native data acquisition based on ODF and SeedLink is extended by the integration of CAPS, a multiformat acquisition platform allowing the integration of additional sensor types like the GNSS sensors developed by YET within the project. Data from the seismic sensors are streamed to the TURNkey platform. The low-cost sensors allow setting up of dense networks, which are the basis for the planned EEW engine. The high density of PGA measurements in combination with the smartphone-based and eyewitness observations give valuable input for the RRE engine. The observations are transferred via QuakeLink streaming real-time earthquake information and observations to the scientific engine, as shown in Figure 3. The real-time data acquisition and earthquake detection/processing system is based on SeisComP, an open-source seismic real-time data processing, and analysis framework.

In addition to the newly-deployed conventional TURNkey RS4D sensors, the existing sensors in the city of Bucharest in Romania (TB 1) have been incorporated into the TURNkey system, primarily through radon measurement devices to contribute to OEF research. The radon measurements from existing sensors are provided on an FTP server. This non-seismic radon data is retrieved by an FTP CAPS plugin and is pushed into the TURNkey CAPS system.

The smartphone-based data, i.e., a felt report, together with other felt report providers (UNIBG, USGS, and EMSC) are collected and processed through QuakeLink. QuakeLink is a protocol and implementation providing a telnet interface for massive data requests and an HTTP interface similar to FDSN web services (GET + POST) as a more convenient request type. It supports real-time and time window-based felt report requests, archiving, and felt report exchange via secure SSL encrypted connections with authentication. The felt reports are used in the RRE process as input to the shake-map algorithm. The data goes into the Bayesian shake map algorithm, as a list of intensity and geographic position entries. One for each observation.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the station view of the TURNkey platform in Europe. On the left side, the real-time stream of station R7971 located in the middle of France is shown. The colours of the triangles represent the recent ground motion, the red triangles indicate seismic triggers from the automatic processing

The eyewitness observations (e.g., damage states from a field survey) can be reported through either the TURNkey platform or the TURNkey smartphone app if the user is properly registered by at least one control room. Moreover, the registered user can also obtain information on the earthquake and have an early warning feature for the aftershock. The eyewitness observations are used in the RRE process as input to update the risk and loss estimates and the corresponding maps. The end-users have the possibility to check the impacted area/infrastructure, verifying which one is damaged and at which level in real-time.

It is worth clarifying that the shake map area is defined as the area of primary interest for hazard, risk, and loss computations while the study area is defined as the area of interest for seismic events affecting the shake map area. Taking the synthetic “Icelandopolis” as an example, as shown in Figure 4, the study area (mostly used in the OEF process) covers a larger area than the shake map area. The background seismicity area is defined as the area covered by the seismic zonation map.

Figure 4. Study area, shake map area, and background seismicity area.

2.2 Scientific engines and processing

The core processes handled by the scientific engine are OEF, EEW, RRE, and simulation. In the earthquake disaster management timeline, as shown in Figure 5, before an earthquake, the end-user can simulate various earthquake scenarios to facilitate disaster planning. The OEF process can be run on request to forecast the seismic hazard before an earthquake. The EEW process is triggered after an earthquake potentially causing a severe impact. If the PGA is above a certain threshold for a site, the RRE process is activated and it continuously runs throughout the disaster management cycle (e.g., weeks after the mainshock or until the user resets the system). The OEF process will be triggered after an earthquake to forecast heightened seismic hazard using the newly collected event catalogue during the short-term disaster response phase. To support the core functionalities of the scientific engine, the processing engine with several infrastructure components are developed, including the PostgreSQL database, the REST API server, the GeoServer, and the notification server.

Figure 5. Illustration of the chronological sequence of Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF), Earthquake Early Warning (EEW), and Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE) and simulation.

2.2.1 Event Listener engine

The event listener engine continuously listens to the QuakeLink for new events above a given magnitude threshold (causing potential damage states), within a predefined monitoring area. As shown in Figure 6, when such an event arrives its location and magnitude are uploaded to the TURNkey database, and a notification will be sent to the EEW engine. Moreover, when new instrumental measurements and/or DYFI reports arrive, the event estimation is updated and thus the QuakeLink is updated, which in turn is heard by the event listener engine.

The delay caused by communication between QuakeLink and the event listener should normally be of the order of fractions of a second. However, it depends on a working network connection.

Figure 6. Event listener engine

2.2.2 EEW engine

As shown in Figure 7, the EEW engine continuously listens for new notifications for new and updated events from the event listener engine. When an event notification arrives, the ground-motion intensity measures (IMs) (e.g., PGAs) are computed over the shake map area, which is then compared to the threshold (defined at the building level or the global level). If no thresholds are surpassed, no action is taken, but if at least one threshold is surpassed (i.e., an event may cause damages to the building stock), the EEW engine produces notifications for the RRE engine (to start processing) and the GUI (a warning about the event in terms of estimated location and magnitude). In addition, an estimated “most affected area” is computed as a polygon/contour to be sent to GUI. Subsequently, the engine enters an “aftershock mode”, where OEF computations will be performed regularly using the newly-collected event catalogue, and new events are treated as aftershocks

The EEW computations may take a few seconds, and when finished, continue listening for new events and updates. If events are queuing up, we prioritize new events before updates.

Figure 7. The EEW engine

2.2.3 RRE engine

As shown in Figure 8, the RRE engine continuously listens for new notifications from the EEW engine. When receiving the first notification, the RRE engine computes a quick shake map in terms of PGA and European Macroseismic Scale Intensity (EMS-98) based on the event magnitude and location and the selected GMMs. On the subsequent updates, it applies the Bayesian shake map algorithm delivered by BRGM to update the shake maps, considering the observed ground-motion IMs at stations and DYFI reports.

To be able to include PGA values from sensors, the SeisComP utility *scwffparam* is used. It takes as input the inventory obtained from QuakeLink or FDSNW service, the event id and event file, address to the GMP caps-server, and compute PGA (and PGV, PSA) values going in to the Bayesian shake map algorithm (currently, only PGA values are used).

If DYFI data for the event are available, these data can be accessed via GMP Quakelink DYFI-API and fed into the Bayesian shake map algorithm.

The generated shake maps are uploaded to the GeoServer and a notification is sent to the GUI notifying that the shake maps are available. The risk and loss estimations are based on the shake map. When risk and loss results are computed, they are uploaded to the database, and the GUI is notified. Then, damage and loss maps for the exposure data are uploaded to GeoServer.

The RRE engine may take a few minutes to finalize, and this may cause queueing up of input events, requiring prioritization. Like in the EEW engine, events not previously processed are prioritized.

Figure 8. The RRE engine

2.2.4 OEF engine

Contrary to the real-time EEW and RRE pipelines that quickly support the first responders after an earthquake, the OEF engine assesses the seismic hazard within the prescribed forecasting time interval based on the constantly updated event catalogue. As shown in Figure 9, the OEF computations of the seismic hazard will start immediately after the main event was accepted in the EEW engine. This computation uses at least 20 events from the existing catalogue before the time of running, and the results are maps showing the probability of a strong ground motion within the next day.

This process is computationally intensive and expensive, and may - depending on the size of exposure data and study area, and processing power assigned to the process - requires a run time of up to several hours. It will update the estimates repeatedly until the user resets the system.

Figure 9. The OEF engine

2.2.5 Processing engine infrastructural components

The processing engine is a distributed system, with multiple components running in different processes supporting the core functionalities of the scientific engine. The key infrastructure is the PostgreSQL database, which hosts all states and data shared by the engine processes/components. Other infrastructures are mainly to support the communication with the GUI.

2.2.5.1 Database

A PostgreSQL database stores and organizes both static and dynamic data (e.g., hazard data, exposure data, vulnerability data, real-time instrumental data), processing parameters (e.g., selection of fragility functions), and processing results (e.g., physical and social vulnerability estimations). This is the core of the system through which all of the internal process communication is streamed. As shown in Figure 10, the main functionalities are:

- **Notifications:** A component notifies another component about a state change or availability of new data.
- **Insert/Update:** Write new or updated information to the database.
- **Request/Get:** Request data from the database.

Figure 10. The PostgreSQL database

2.2.5.2 REST API Server

The REST API Server is the web API through which external applications (that is the end-user GUI) can communicate with the engine to request simulations, ask for processing results or site contents or update damage and loss data in the system, as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. The REST API server

2.2.5.3 GeoServer

GeoServer is a WMS server managing the geographic maps generated in the engine, as shown in Figure 12. Map layers can be represented as raster or vector data in a range of formats. By combining layers and styles, the WMS services provide georeferenced images to web front-ends. See <http://geoserver.org/> for more details.

Figure 12. The GeoServer

2.2.5.4 Notification server

The notification server listens for notifications from the processing components, collects data from the database, and sends the notification on to the GUI process to alert the users, as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. The notification server

2.3 Outputs and Communication

This section describes the outputs presented in the TURNkey platform and the communication module (e.g., data transition between the scientific engine and the GUI, the information dissemination through GUI to the civil protection and first responders). Examples of outputs are illustrated in Chapter 4.

2.3.1 EEW

The EEW process provides the hazard results quickly. In the immediate period after an earthquake, the EEW process will send out visual and audio alerts on the TURNkey platform. The alert information includes the event magnitude and the distance from the epicentre to the end-user location. In the meantime, the most affected region highlighted by a polygon will be available from the map view. The most affected region is defined by the area with $PGA \geq$ pre-defined PGA threshold in %g. The PGA values are estimated using GMMs, magnitude, and distance from the earthquake, which is an efficient way to evaluate the level of potential damage. No spatial correlation is considered in this process.

Given the initial estimates of the seismic hazard and the potential impact, the end-user can, through the platform, disseminate the information within or across the relevant organization and send out messages to the public on a social media platform. According to the pre-defined protocols, various threshold-based risk-mitigation measures would be triggered automatically.

2.3.2 RRE

The RRE process provides both the updated hazard results and the risk and loss results. The hazard results are presented as the updated shake map of PGA and EMS-98 macroseismic intensity, based on the Bayesian shake map algorithm developed at BRGM, considering instrument recordings and DYFI data, if provided by the QuakeLink. The spatial correlation is considered in this process.

The RRE risk and loss results can be presented in both the map view and the dashboard for Essential Facilities (Efs) by building, Critical Infrastructure Systems (CISs) by infrastructure, and General Buildings (GBs) on averaged over geographic regions. Based on the occupancy class, the presented information can vary to better facilitate the emergency response. The risk and loss results consist of information on physical and social vulnerabilities. The damage and loss estimation for the mainshock can be updated at a discrete property location or for a geographic region where eyewitness observations are available.

Physical vulnerability information includes:

- The EMS-98 damage grade: DS0: No damage; DS1: Negligible to slight damage; DS2: Moderate damage; DS3: Substantial to heavy damage; DS4: Very heavy damage; DS5: Destruction
- Expected damages: expected number of buildings per damage grade
- Functionality: from 0%: no functionality to 100%: full functionality
- Economic loss: total economic loss in millions of Euro (M€)
- Vulnerability level: green-yellow-red bar, corresponding to safe-warrant-unsafe state.

Social vulnerability information includes:

- Expected casualty: expected number of people per severity level

- Homeless: Number of homeless people
- Shelter: Number of displaced households

Through the TURNkey platform and the app, the end-user can submit eyewitness reports to update the risk and loss estimates. The reported information includes the basic information on the building (i.e., locations and occupancy class), the observed physical and social vulnerabilities (e.g., damage state, functionality level, casualty, number of homeless and number of shelters), as well as pictures of the damaged building used for further verification.

Similar to the EEW process, the end-user can disseminate information to the relevant organizations/personnel and the public through the platform. If defined in the protocol, risk-mitigation measures can be triggered automatically.

2.3.3 OEF (aftershock)

An OEF process presents both long-term (time-independent) and short-term (time-dependent) daily probability of exceeding a certain PGA level and also computes the spatial distribution of estimated increased seismic probability of an earthquake happening in the next 24 hours in the study area.

The computational cost of this step is heavy and may take several hours, depending on computer resources, the size of area and the exposure data (if site-specific seismic hazard analysis is needed).

The OEF is updated daily and thus constantly communicates with the QuakeLink and/or CAPS to request the event catalogue and/or non-seismic radon data. Once the OEF hazard results are updated, they will be sent to the GUI promptly.

2.3.4 Event simulation

An event simulation answers the question about what will happen if an event of magnitude M happens at horizontal position (*latitude, longitude*) and, depth D . Essentially, this process emulates the first iteration of the real-time EEW-RRE pipeline. Compared to the real-time operation of the TURNkey platform, the event simulation process is simplified in two aspects: (1) all events within the study area are accepted by the EEW; and (2) the RRE engine will always generate damage and loss results.

The user defines the event information (i.e., location, magnitude, and hypocentre depth) in the GUI, which is sent to the scientific engine via the REST API. The REST API stores the simulated event in the database and produces a notification for the EEW engine. The EEW engine then generates an event alert, computes and reports “most affected area” and activates the RRE engine. Subsequently, the RRE engine first computes shake maps in terms of PGA and macroseismic intensity based on magnitude, location, and GMMs and produces a report about the hazard results to the GUI, and, finally, the RRE engine generates risk and loss estimations and updates the database, and produces a GUI notification. The maps of the risk and loss results are also generated and uploaded to the GeoServer for the GUI.

3 PLATFORM INSTALLATION

3.1 Instrumentation Setup and Real-time Data Transmission/Acquisition

Within the TURNkey project, extensive sensor development was performed. Prototypes of the low-cost RS4D sensor can be mounted on a wall which requires no horizontal space and the usage of a wireless connection in combination of the use of the power socket for electric power and the mounting remove the need for cabling. Moreover, the RaspberryShake unit has been integrated with the CAPS based data acquisition and other algorithms. Especially the optimization of the MiniSeed records through the reduction of the packet size reduces drastically the data delay improving the EEW capability of the RS4D. The use of the MiniSeed format instead of using a different format ensures the compatibility to many existing seismic data analysis software packages. This applies not only for the seismic data, also the GNSS data is available in MiniSeed format. The TURNkey RS4D firmware handling seismic and GNSS through the CAPS server on the RS4D, will be partly integrated in the native RS4D firmware. This is planned in April/May 2022 by RaspberryShake. The instrument setup and real-time data transmission/acquisition can be found in deliverable D6.1 (Weber & Curone, 2021).

3.2 EEW, RRE, and OEF Engines Setup

3.2.1 Prerequisites

- PostgreSQL Database server with database-administrator (DBA) privileges
- Docker
- Docker orchestration system
 - o Docker-compose,
 - o Docker swarm,
 - o AWS ECS
 - o Or other

The software has been tested on AWS ECS and docker-compose.

3.2.2 Engine docker images

Access to the Docker images required for running the engine and a sample docker-compose.yml file can be received from NORSAR together with a template dataset.

Docker-compose file will need to be adapted for use on the local system.

A script to launch a container for importing data to the database are also be provided.

3.2.3 Installing data for engine

Installing data consists of three main steps:

- Create and initialize the database
- Install static data
- Install site-specific data

There is unfortunately no graphical user interface to do the setup, but a set of scripts and template text files are provided.

3.2.3.1 *Setting up the environment*

The scripts to be used for database setup are tested under Debian Linux

A working environment can be obtained by running a bash shell in the EEW docker image:

```
docker run --it --v /install_code:/path/to/turnkey_install_code ${CR_URL}/turnkey-eew:latest bash
```

3.2.3.2 *Create database*

It is recommended that the PostgreSQL server is run on a machine dedicated to that purpose.

Use `pgsql` to create a new database for storing Turnkey site data. See <https://www.postgresql.org/docs/9.0/sql-createdatabase.html>

3.2.3.3 *Initialize database*

To initialize the database, the user will need a bash shell, and database connection parameters in environment:

```
#!/bin/bash
export POSTGRES_HOST=your.postgres.host.domain.xx
export POSTGRES_DBNAME=your_database_name
export POSTGRES_PORT=5432
export POSTGRES_USER=your_pg_username
bash /install_code/initialize_db.sh
```

3.2.3.4 *Install static data*

To install static data, the user will also need to add a password to the environment:

```
export POSTGRES_PASSWORD=your_pg_password
```

In addition, add an environment variable where input data is stored

```
export INPUT_DATA_PATH=/path/to/db_static_data/
export VULNERABILITY_TOP_PATH=/path/to/oq_vulnerability_model/
export HB_CI_FRAGILITY_PATH=/path/to/Fragility_Functions_HB_CI/
export POINT_IND_FRAGILITY=/path/to/point_ind_fragility_function/
```

where

- **INPUT_DATA_PATH** is the top-level directory for standard input data
- **VULNERABILITY_TOP_PATH** is the top path containing vulnerability data
- **HB_CI_FRAGILITY_PATH** is the path to a directory containing fragility for infrastructures
- **POINT_IND_FRAGILITY** is the path to a directory containing industrial fragility functions

Then call the script:

```
python <path>/db_init_scripts/import_static_data.py
```

After this, the user should be able to install the site-specific data

3.2.3.5 Install site-specific data

Site-specific data includes exposure data, geocodes, hazard computation input, risk computation parameters, technical parameters, and connection information to internal and external components (e.g., Cloud GUI, QuakeLink servers, GeoServer). First, all input must be collected and stored in a directory that can be reached from the process to install the data. Then, a setup file is specified. This section describes the required information in the setup file. An example site for installation is available on demand.

3.2.3.5.1 Site

This section defines the main site parameters, where the *site* defines the area of interest and ties the information for one engine together.

```
[site]
name = Icelandopolis_2040
area = [-23.538, 63.509, -20.403, 64.671]
eew_threshold = 3
risk_parameters_name = DEFAULT
shake_map_parameters_name = DEFAULT
oef_parameters_name = DEFAULT
seismicity_info_parameters_name = DEFAULT
server_product_site_connection_name = DEFAULT
```

- **name:** is the name identifying the site
- **area:** Bounding box [min_longitude, min_latitude, max_longitude, max_latitude] of the shake map area.
- **eew_threshold:** Global PGA limit given in % of g for launching an alert.
- **risk_parameters_name:** Name of risk parameters parameter set. See further below.
- **oef_parameters_name:** Name of OEF computation parameter set. See further below.
- **seismicity_info_parameters_name:** Name of seismicity_info_parameters. See further below.
- **server_product_site_connection_name:** Name of parameters defining servers to communicate with. See section 3.2.3.5.9 for more information.

3.2.3.5.2 GeoServer connection

This section specifies connection properties for a GeoServer instance. Typically, the “service” part should never change.

```
[geoserver_connection]
name = geoserver_connection
protocol = https
host = my.server.com
port = 443
service = /geoserver/rest
server_user = admin
```

3.2.3.5.3 Event connection

These are connection details for the QuakeLink service where we can query for events

```
[event_connection]
name = event_connection
protocol = https
host = phobos.gempa.de
service = /quakelink/events/query
port = 443
```

3.2.3.5.4 Inventory connection

This is the connection details for the QuakeLink (see <https://phobos.gempa.de/fdsnws/>) service where we can request station information.

```
[inventory_connection]
name = inventory_connection
protocol = https
host = phobos.gempa.de
service = /quakelink/fdsnws/station/1/query
port = 443
```

3.2.3.5.5 Event stream connection

This is the connection details for the GMP *qltool* used by the event listener to listen for event updates. The protocol is in this case a secure or insecure transmission control protocol (TCP) connection. It is needed to set the protocol to something ending with *s* for a secure connection, and not with *s* for unsecured connections.

```
[event_stream_connection]
name = event_stream_connection
protocol = tcps
host = phobos.gempa.de
port = 18012
server_user = norsar
```

3.2.3.5.6 DYFI Connection

This is the GMP QuakeLink connection for obtaining DYFI data.

```
[dyfi_connection]
name = dyfi_connection
protocol = https
host = phobos.gempa.de
service = /quakelink/dyfi/query
server_user = norsar
port = 443
```

3.2.3.5.7 Instrument data connection

This is the connection to access GMP CAPS data (to get, for example, radon).

```
[instrument_data_connection]
name = instrument_data_connection
protocol = capss
host = phobos.gempa.de
port = 18004
server user = turnkey
```

3.2.3.5.8 GUI Connection

This is the listener API for the external module receiving notifications (provided by B80).

```
[gui_connection]
name = gui_connection
protocol = https
host = emma2cmapiturnkey.azurewebsites.net
port = 443
Server_user =
```

3.2.3.5.9 Site connection

The site connection setup aims to connect the site with different server connections. The parameters can usually be kept as they are. Make sure that the name is the same as the name referred to in Section 3.2.3.5.1.

```
[site_connection]
name = DEFAULT
geoserver_name = geoserver_connection
event_name = event_connection
event_stream_name = event_stream_connection
inventory_name = inventory_connection
dyfi_name = dyfi_connection
instrument_data_name = instrument_data_connection
gui_name = gui_connection
```

3.2.3.5.10 OEF parameters

These are computation parameters for the OEF processes. Make sure that name is consistent with the name referred to in Section 3.2.3.5.1. A complete list of parameters is presented in Table 1.

```
[oef_parameters]
name = DEFAULT
user_shapefile_proj = EPSG:4326
aftershock_zone_bbox = [-22.900, 63.690, -20.000, 64.200]
delta_grid = [0.0227, 0.01]
column_label_for_a_value = a_val
column_label_for_b_value = b_val
flag_user_defined_seismicity = True
im_period = 0
im_range = [0.005, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05, 0.07, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 1.2]
m_min = 4.5
maxmag=[ 7.0, 6.8, 7.2, 0]
wmaxmag=[0.7, 0.15, 0.15, 0]
hypodepth=[ 5.672, 0, 0]
whdepth=[1.0, 0, 0]
fault_mechanism_weight_ss=1
fault_mechanism_weight_nf=0
fault_mechanism_weight_tf=0
m_upper_bound=7.0
flag_non_seismic_input = False
```

Table 1. List of OEF parameters

Attribute Name	Attribute type	Default value	Description
name	string	'Icelando polis_2040'	User-defined name
aftershock_zone_bbox	List[float] (4)	[-22.900, 63.690, -20.000, 64.200]	This is the area where we are interested in events
delta_grid	List[float] (2)	[0.1,0.1]	Grid dx, dy (in degrees)
m_min	float	4.5	The minimum magnitude for PSHA
im_period	float	0	The considered period of spectral ordinate. 0 is PGA
im_range	List[float] (10)	[0.005, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05, 0.07, 0.1,	A list of IM threshold in g considered in the PSHA

		0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 1.2]	
flag_non_seismic_input	bool	False	Not relevant everywhere. True if radon data is to be used
non_seismic_wmean	float	1	Weighting for the mean activity rate. Between [0, 1}
non_seismic_wmean_std	float	1	Weighting for the mean + standard deviation activity rate Between [0, 1] Sum of this and the above must = 1
non_seismic_wseismic	float	1	Weighting for the seismic data. Between [0, 1]. Only applicable if using nonseismic data
non_seismic_wnon_seismic	float	1	Weighting for the non-seismic data. Between [0, 1]. Sum of this and the above must = 1 Only applicable if using non-seismic data
maxmag	List[float] (4)	[7.0, 6.8, 7.2, 0]	Four magnitude branches, for example [4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0]
wmaxmag	List[float] (4)	[0.7, 0.15, 0.15, 0]	Weights of each magnitude branch. Should sum up to 1.0
hypodepth	List[float] (3)	[5.672, 0, 0]	3 hypocentral depth branches in km
whdepth	List[float] (3)	[1.0, 0, 0]	Weights of each depth branch. Should sum up to 1.
fault_mechanism_weight_ss	float	1	Weighting for strike-slip fault, In [0,1]
fault_mechanism_weight_nf	float	0	Weighting for normal fault, In [0, 1]
fault_mechanism_weight_tf	float	0	Weighting for thrust fault, In [0,1] Sum of the three must = 1
m_upper_bound	float	7.0	The upper magnitude considered in the Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequence (ETAS) sequence generation
use_sub_sequence	int	False	
flag_user_defined_seismicity	bool	False	True if using a country-specific zonation map. Otherwise, use European
column_label_for_a_value	string	""	If using customary zonation shape map, this is the field name for field containing a-value
column_label_for_b_value	string	""	If using customary zonation shape map, this is the field name for field containing b-value

user_shapefile_proj	string	""	Projection of user shapefile: EPSG code
oef_gmm	List[OefGmm]	["AbrahamsonEtAl 2014"]	List of user GMMs

3.2.3.5.11 Seismicity info parameters

These are extra site parameters, as listed in Table 2:

```
[seismicity_info_params]
name = Default
area = [-22.900, 63.690, -20.000, 64.200]
image_size = [350, 450]
min_magnitude_report = 3
min_magnitude_etas_analysis = 3
```

Table 2. Seismicity info parameters

Attribute name	Attribute type	Description
name	string	User-defined name
image_size	List[int] (2)	[nx, ny] gridding resolution of the shake map area
min_magnitude_report	float	The minimum magnitude for sending an event into the system
min_magnitude_etas_analysis	Float [1.5]	The minimum magnitude for ETAS analysis

3.2.3.5.12 Risk parameters

These are computation parameters for SELENA-based damage and loss computations, as listed in Table 3.

```
[risk_parameters]
name=DEFAULT
damage_probabilities_estimation_method=Fragility_Capacity
physical_vulnerabilities_estimation_method=Fragility_DamageToLoss
performance_point_computation_method=N2
topographic_amplification=Eurocode
spectrum_code=EC8Type1
```

Table 3. Risk parameters

Attribute	Values	Default value
damage_probabilities_estimation_method	<input type="radio"/> Fragility_Capacity <input type="radio"/> Macroseismic	Fragility_Capacity
physical_vulnerabilities_estimation_method	<input type="radio"/> Fragility -Damage-to-Loss <input type="radio"/> Vulnerability	Fragility - Damage-to-Loss
performance_point_computation_method	<input type="radio"/> N2 <input type="radio"/> IMP_DCM	
Topography_amplification_method	<input type="radio"/> Eurocode <input type="radio"/> Italian <input type="radio"/> Molina 2016	Eurocode
Spectrum_code	<input type="radio"/> Site_specific <input type="radio"/> EC8Type1 <input type="radio"/> EC8Type2 <input type="radio"/> USA IBC-2006	Site_specific

3.2.3.5.13 Shake map parameters

These are computation parameters for the Bayesian shake map process and the complete list of parameters is shown in Table 4. It is worth noting that the Bayesian shake map algorithm includes the conversion equation for the Modified Mercalli Intensity Scale (MMI).

```
[shake_map_params]
name = DEFAULT
gmice = GMICECaprioetal2015
correlation_distance = 20
mmi_factors = [1,1]
alpha_values = [2.27, -1.361]
beta_values = [1.647, 3.882]
mmi_limit = 4.902
modxy = 1
modpga = 1
modmmi = 1
mod_grid_mmi = 1
influence_function = 0
influence_distance = 100
```

Table 4. Shake map parameters

Attribute Name	Attribute type	Default value	Description
name	string	Default	User-defined name
gmice	string	GMICECaprioetal2015	Ground Motion to intensity conversion equation (GMICE) name. Supported values: [GMICECaprioetal2015, GMICESouriau2006]
correlation_distance	float	20	Correlation distance for the spatial correlation relation. in km
mmi_factors	List[float] (2)	[1, 1]	Influence of seismic intensity observations. $\sigma_{MMI1} = 0.7 * \text{factormmi1}$ and $\sigma_{MMI2} = 1.4 * \text{factormmi2}$. Default factormmi1 (1 & 2) = 1
alpha values	List[float] (2)	[2.27, -1.361]	$\text{mmi} \leq \text{mmi lim}$, GMICE parameter
beta values	List[float] (2)	[1.647, 3.882]	$\text{mmi} \leq \text{mmi lim}$, GMICE parameter
mmi limit	float	4.9052	MMI limit for piecewise GMICE
modxy	float	1	Influence of observations on the global model. By default $\text{mod}(xy \ \& \ pga \ \& \ mmi) = 1$. if i is a point on the grid: $\sigma_{Eta}[i] = \text{sig_inter} / \text{math.log}(10) * \text{modxy}$.
modpga	float	1	if i is an observation of PGA: $\sigma_{Eta}[i] = \text{sig_inter} / \text{math.log}(10) * \text{modpga}$.
modmmi	float	1	if i is an observation of intensity: $\sigma_{Eta}[i] = \text{sig_inter} / \text{math.log}(10) * \text{modmmi}$
mod_grid_mmi	float	0	Correction of the intensity grid. $\text{grid_MMI} = \text{grid_MMI} + \text{modGridMMI} * \text{sigMMI}$ with $\text{sigMMI} = 0.25$. Default $\text{modGridMMI} = 0$

influence_function	int	0	Application of an influence function according to the deviation from the source or the deviation from the global model. Default: no influence functions: Function_influence = 0. If Function_influence = 1: if the point Distance_influence then $\sigma_{\eta} [i] = \sigma_{\eta} [i] * \text{math.exp} (\text{distVal} / \text{Distance influence})$
influence_distance	float	100	Distance of influence according to the deviation from the source. Default Distance influence = 100 km

3.2.3.5.14 Site effect code maps

Given a boundary PGA value, this is a lookup table to map between a site classification and the site amplification factor for PGA below the boundary value and PGA above the boundary value. The data is represented as a list of lists, where each record consist of [classification, amplification_below_boundary, amplification_above_boundary]. The site classification is defined according to Table 5.

```
[site_effect_code_maps]
code = [
  [1,1.94,1.94],
  [2,1.70,1.70],
  [3,1.54,1.54],
  [4,1.42,1.42],
  [5,1.28,1.28],
  [6,1.16,1.16],
  [7,1.06,1.06],
  [8,1.00,1.00],
  [0,1.00,1.00]]
```

Table 5. Site classification

Site classification	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
V _{S30} (m/s)	<180	180-240	240-300	300-360	360-490	490-620	620-760	760>

3.2.3.5.15 Station file

Define the full path to a text file containing stations to be used:

```
[station_file]
file =
/path/to/site_data_generation/Synthetic_Iceland/other_data/current_station_list.txt
```

The format of the station file is comma-separated values (CSV) format with comma-separators, where columns are Latitude, Longitude, station code, V_{S30} at the station, Network code, and Description.

```
"Lat","Lon","Code","Vel","Network","Description"
63.975,-22.5118,R0050,284.116943359375,AM,Raspberry Shake Citizen Science
Station 4Dv7
65.9932,-17.37615,R08B0,413.671478271484,AM,Raspberry Shake Citizen Science
Station 4Dv7
...
```

3.2.3.5.16 Geoarea files

A shapefile that must contain information about geoarea name, latitude, and longitude in addition to polygons defining geocode borders. In this section, full file paths must be given as well as shapefile attributes representing name, latitude, and longitude for geocodes.

```
[geocode_files]
geoshape_file =
/vcs/vetle/Workspace/site_data_generation/Synthetic_Iceland/shapes/Iceland_Admin
Level-2
attr_geocode_name = GeoUnitId
attr_geocode_lat = CentroidLat
attr_geocode_lon = CentroidLon
```

3.2.3.5.17 Occupancy ratio

This is described in its own settings file that is referenced by the top-level file:

```
[occupancy_ratio]
file = occupancy_ratio.ini
```

The occupancy ratio file describes relative occupancy for each occupancy class (level 1), and time intervals for day, night and transit times.

```
[RES]
occupancy_day=0.90
occupancy_night=0.98
occupancy_transit=0.36
start_time_day=[08:00:00]
end_time_day=[16:00:00]
start_time_night=[20:00:00]
end_time_night=[06:00:00]
start_time_transit=[06:00:00, 16:00:00]
end_time_transit=[08:00:00, 20:00:00]
```

3.2.3.5.18 Occupancy state exception

This is to describe exceptions to the general occupancy rules. These exceptional occupancy rules will be applied to the user-specified Geocode and occupancy class, as defined in <GEOCODE_NAME>_<OCCUPANCY_CLASS>. The example below defines an exception for Geocode “MyPlace” and Occupancy Class COM.

```
[MyPlace_COM]
start_time_day=[08:00:00]
end_time_day=[16:00:00]
start_time_night=[20:00:00]
end_time_night=[06:00:00]
start_time_transit=[06:00:00, 16:00:00]
end_time_transit=[08:00:00, 20:00:00]
```

3.2.3.5.19 Ground Motion Models

Users can specify up to five Ground Motion Models and their corresponding weight for the hazard computations. The OpenQuake library of GMMs is integrated into the scientific engine.

```
[gmm]
G1 = KowsariEtAl2020_Y5_C4C5C6
W1 = 0.5
G2 = KowsariEtAl2020_Y1_C3_AB10
W2 = 0.2
G3 = KowsariEtAl2020_Y3_C4C5_LL08
W3 = 0.2
G4 = KowsariEtAl2020_Y2_C4_Am05
W4 = 0.05
```

```
G5 = KowsariEtAl2020_Y4_C4C5_Zh06
W5 = 0.05
```

3.2.3.5.20 Topology description

This is used in damage and loss computations to account for the topography effect for buildings, as shown in Table 6.

```
[topology_description]
name = DEFAULT
max_height = 0
semi_length = 0
topographic_amplification = Eurocode
geometry_code = plane
type_of_crest = NoCrest
structure_location = Top
```

Table 6. Topography parameter description

Attribute Name	Description
max_height	maximum height in m of the topographic feature
semi_length	Half-width in m of the geometry (also known as semi length)
topographic_amplification	1.Eurocode: Eurocode Topography amplification method 2. Italian: Italian code Topography amplification method 3.Molina 2016: Molina et al. (2016) period-dependent relationship
geometry_code	label for the simplified geometry: plane; hills, slopes
type_of_crest	Label for type of crest: Sharp, Soft, NoCrest
structure_location	Label for the structure location: Top, Middle, Toe/foot

3.2.3.5.21 Exposure data

List of excel sheets specifying general buildings, essential facilities and, critical infrastructure systems.

```
[sera_building_files]
general_buildings = [
[/path/to/site_data_generation/Synthetic_Iceland/exposure/Exposure_GB_toinsert.xlsx, Sheet1]]
essential_facilities = [
[/path/to//site_data_generation/Synthetic_Iceland/exposure/Exposure_EF_toinsert_small.xlsx, Sheet1]]
critical_systems = [
[/path/to/site_data_generation/Synthetic_Iceland/exposure/Exposure_CIS_toinsert_small.xlsx, Sheet1]]
```

An excel sheet for buildings should contain columns for (red means mandatory information, yellow means mandatory for General Building Stock), as shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Exposure data

Fields	Descriptions	Mandatory	Optional
USER_ID	User-defined ID	✓	
SERVICE	one of [General Building Stock, Essential	✓	

	Facilities, Critical Infrastructure Systems]		
LONGITUDE	Longitude in deg	✓	
LATITUDE	Latitude in deg	✓	
TAXONOMY	SERA or GEM taxonomy	✓	
MACRO_TAXONOMY	Taxonomy description		
BUILDINGS	number of buildings	✓	
DWELLINGS	number of dwellings	✓	
OCCUPANCY1	Occupancy class 1	✓	
OCCUPANCY2	Occupancy class 2	✓	
OCCUPANCY3	Occupancy class 3, only needed for critical infrastructure systems	✓	
OCCUPANCY_TYPE	Occupancy class description		✓
SETTLEMENT_TYPE	Settlement class description		✓
AREA_PER_DWELLING_SQM	Area per dwelling in m ²	✓	
COST_PER_AREA_EUR	Cost per area in EUR €	✓	
TOTAL_REPL_COST_EUR	The total cost of replacement in EUR €	✓	
COST_STRUCTURAL_EUR	Structural cost in EUR (necessary to get economic estimates out)		✓
COST_NONSTRUCTURAL_EUR	Nonstructural cost in EUR		✓
COST_CONTENTS_EUR	Contents cost in EUR		✓
OCCUPANTS_PER_ASSET	Total number of occupants per asset Necessary for general buildings	✓	
OCCUPANTS_PER_ASSET_DAY	Number of occupants per asset in the daytime (10:00 am) (Necessary for casualty information)		✓
OCCUPANTS_PER_ASSET_NIGHT	Number of occupants per asset in nighttime (02:00 am)		✓
OCCUPANTS_PER_ASSET_TRANSIT	Number of occupants per asset in transit time (05:00 pm)		✓
OCCUPANTS_PER_ASSET_AVERAGE	The average number of occupants per asset		✓

ID_2	Administration level 2 ID (geoarea)	✓	
AdminLevel_2	Administration level 2 description	✓	
ID_1	Administration level 1 ID		✓
AdminLevel_1	Administration level 1 description		✓
VULNERABILITY_INDEX	Vulnerability index between [0,1]	✓	
NAME	Name of the building	✓	
DESCRIPTION	Description of the building		✓
VS30	Average shear-wave velocity at the building location	✓	

3.2.3.5.22 V_{S30} file

A GeoTIFF file with V_{S30} values at least covering the study area.

```
[vs30_file]
file = /path/to/Workspace/site_data_generation/Synthetic_Iceland/vs30/VS30.tif
```

3.2.3.5.23 Shape files representing seismicity models

```
[seismicity_shape_files]
file =
/path/to/Workspace/site_data_generation/Synthetic_Iceland/shapes/SeisZonesIce_11
20_Model2

[seismic_zonation_folder]
folder =
/path/to/Workspace/site_data_generation/Synthetic_Iceland/shapes/ASModelVer61

[seismicity_rate]
file =
/path/to/Workspace/site_data_generation/Synthetic_Iceland/shapes/SEIFA_2013_Crus
tal_v6.1
```

3.2.3.5.24 Mappings from taxonomy to vulnerability models

These are mappings defining what vulnerability functions to use for given taxonomies, and weights for each function.

```
[taxonomy_fragility]
file = taxonomy_fragility.ini

[taxonomy_damage_to_loss]
file = taxonomy_damage_to_loss.ini

[taxonomy_vulnerability]
file = taxonomy_vulnerability.ini

[taxonomy_capacity]
file = taxonomy_capacity.ini
```

```
[system_type_fragility]
file = system_type_fragility.ini
```

Example of taxonomy - fragility mapping:

```
[M4]          # Massive stone
F1 = Rota et al (2010) - Masonry
W1 = 1

[M5-LR]       # Un-reinforced Masonry with old bricks low rise
F1 = HAZUS URML - Low code
W1 = 0.5
F2 = HAZUS URML - Precode
W2 = 0.5

[M5-MR]       # Un-reinforced Masonry with old bricks mid-rise
F1 = HAZUS URMM - Low code
W1 = 0.5
F2 = HAZUS URMM - Precode
W2 = 0.5
```

Example of taxonomy – damage to loss mapping

```
[RC8-LR]     # Precast concrete walls low rise
F1 = Kappos et al. (2006) - RC buildings
W1 = 1
F2 =
W2 =

[RC8-MR]     # Precast concrete walls mid-rise
F1 = Kappos et al. (2006) - RC buildings
W1 = 1
F2 =
W2 =
```

Example of taxonomy – vulnerability mapping

```
[M5-LR]       # Un-reinforced Masonry with old bricks low rise
F1 = MUR/CLBRS/H:1
W1 = 0.5
F2 = MUR/CLBRS/H:3-4
W2 = 0.5

[M5-MR]       # Un-reinforced Masonry with old bricks mid-rise
F1 = MUR/CLBRS/H:3-4
W1 = 1
F2 =
W2 =
```

Example of taxonomy – capacity mapping:

```
[M5-LR]       # Un-reinforced Masonry with old bricks low rise
F1 = Kappos et al. (2006) - MUR/HEX:2
W1 = 1
F2 =
W2 =

[M5-MR]       # Un-reinforced Masonry with old bricks mid-rise
```

```
F1 = Barbat et al (2006) - MUR/LWAL_Mid-rise (4storeys) - Capacity
W1 = 1
F2 =
W2 =
```

Example of system type – fragility mapping: Sections are defined by occupancy class names at levels 1, 2, 3:

```
[TINF_TIHW_HWBG]      # Highway Bridges
F1 = HAZUS - Bridges - HWB1 - PGA
W1 = 0.5
F2 = HAZUS - Bridges - HWB2 - PGA
W2 = 0.5

[TINF_TIHW_HWTN]     # Tunnels
F1 = HAZUS - Tunnels - Tunnel Bored/Drilled (HTU1) - PGA
W1 = 0.5
F2 = HAZUS - Tunnels - Tunnel Cut & Cover (HTU2) - PGA
W2 = 0.5
```

3.2.4 Running the installer script

After specifying all input in the files described above, we can run an installer. This is currently in the state of a command-line tool that can be used for installing and updating data for the engine:

In the bash shell, go to the /install_data directory. Make sure the setting (.ini) files described above are available in that directory.

```
$ cd /install_data
```

Set environment variables to connect with database

```
$ source environment_vars.sh
```

Start the install script

```
$ turnkey-setup-site my_settings.ini
```

Start by initializing:

```
>: read_import_data all
```

Install all data

```
>: import_data all
```

When later updating:

```
>: read_import_data all
```

List available commands

```
>: ?
```

Check what data is already imported

```
>: check_imported
```

List import status by module

```
>: import_status
```

Check what modules can currently be imported. Some dependencies need to be followed

```
>:import_options
```

List possible sub-modules for the main module

```
>: attributes <module>
```

Update data for a selected module from the user's file settings

>: **update_data** <module> [<submodule>]
 List currently selected data for import by module
 >: **current_data** <module> [<submodule>]
 List data in database by module
 >: **db_data** <module> [<submodule>]
 Delete imported data from DB for module
 >: **delete_import** <module> [<submodule>]

3.2.5 Running the engine for the installed data

Before starting the engine components, leave the docker container.

The engine should ideally be run on a distributed system like docker swarm, AWS ECS or Kubernetes, but the engine can also run on a single host using docker-compose for testing.

3.2.5.1 Launching GeoServer

The role of GeoServer is to host and make geographic maps available for web browsers and GIS, using standardized WMS. Even if we have multiple engines in operation, they can share a single GeoServer instance. Data are organized in *workspaces*, where a workspace in our system may represent an event, OEF simulation, or site, and are named by *Universally Unique Identifiers* (UUIDs).

When a map is uploaded to GeoServer, a reference to that map is stored in the database. The GUI can ask about available maps for an event or simulation through the API server and the GUI will receive a link to the corresponding WMS service.

Instructions for installing and running GeoServer can be found at <https://github.com/kartoza/docker-geoserver>

To achieve the full functionality of the TURNkey platform, the following extensions need to be activated:

- NetCDF: NetCDF-out-plugin, NetCDF-plugin,
- SLD: sldservice-plugin,
- Charts: charts-plugin

In the TURNkey setting, GeoServer does not require access to the database.

An environment *.env* file specifies all the properties of the GeoServer instance (see <https://github.com/kartoza/docker-geoserver> for more information).

Required changes to the defaults are shown below.

```
STABLE_EXTENSIONS=netcdf-plugin,netcdf-out-plugin,sldservice-plugin,charts-plugin
```

Note that if the GeoServer will be exposed to the internet, it must be run under the secure sockets layer (SSL). Environment variable `SSL=True` must be set in the environment. See the documentation on <https://github.com/kartoza/docker-geoserver> for details.

Example docker-compose snippet for launching GeoServer:

```
turnkey_geoserver:
  image: kartoza/geoserver:${GS_VERSION}
  ports:
    - ${GEOSERVER_PORT}:8080
  volumes:
    - geoserver-data:/opt/geoserver/data_dir
  environment:
    - STABLE_EXTENSIONS=netcdf-plugin,charts-plugin,netcdf-out-plugin,sldservice-plugin
    - GEOSERVER_DATA_DIR=${GEOSERVER_DATA_DIR}
    - GEOWEBCACHE_CACHE_DIR=${GEOWEBCACHE_CACHE_DIR}
    - GEOSERVER_ADMIN_PASSWORD=${GEOSERVER_ADMIN_PASSWORD}
    - GEOSERVER_ADMIN_USER=${GEOSERVER_ADMIN_USER}
    - INITIAL_MEMORY=${INITIAL_MEMORY}
    - MAXIMUM_MEMORY=${MAXIMUM_MEMORY}
```

Environment variables `${XXX}` are provided in a `.env` file at the input directory. Recommended values for INITIAL MEMORY and MAXIMUM MEMORY are 2G and 4G respectively

To run the GeoServer with docker-compose:

```
cd <geoserver-top-dir>
docker-compose -f <docker-compose-geoserver>.yml up -d
```

3.2.5.2 Launching engine components

The following services are launched:

- rest: The Web API server serving requests from the GUI module
- notification: The service that sends notifications to the GUI module
- event_listener: The event listener process
- eew: The EEW service
- rre: The RRE service
- oef: The OEF service

The following parameters must be passed as an environment:

- **POSTGRES_HOST**: Hostname of the PostgreSQL server
- **POSTGRES_PORT**: The port on which the PostgreSQL server is listening
- **POSTGRES_DB**: Database name for the engine database
- **POSTGRES_PASSWORD**: Password to access the engine database
- **GEOSERVER_PASSWORD**: Password to the GeoServer admin user
- **EVENT_NETWORK_PASSWORD**: Password for the GMP QuakeLink server as used by *qltool*
- **SITE_NAME**: The name of the site to be served by the engine

3.2.5.2.1 Event listener

Docker-compose snippet for event listener:

```
listener:
  image: ${ECR_URL}/${ECR_STACK_NAME}-rest-server
  entrypoint: ["event_listener"]
  deploy:
    resources:
      limits:
        cpus: 0.5
        memory: 512M
      reservations:
        cpus: 0.25
        memory: 256M
  environment:
    - SITE_NAME=${SITE_NAME}
    - DATABASE_HOST=${POSTGRES_SERVER}
    - DATABASE_USER=${POSTGRES_USER}
    - DATABASE_PORT=${POSTGRES_PORT}
    - DATABASE_DBNAME=${POSTGRES_DB}
    - DATABASE_PWD=${POSTGRES_PASSWORD}
    - EVENT_NETWORK_PASSWORD=${EVENT_NETWORK_PASSWORD}
```

The deploy settings are only valid for docker swarm deployment, but give a hint of the required resources for the event listener. The process is neither memory nor processing-intensive and should be assigned limited resources.

3.2.5.2.2 EEW Process

Docker-compose snippet for EEW process:

```
eew:
  image: ${ECR_URL}/${ECR_STACK_NAME}-eew-worker
  entrypoint: ["eew_controller"]
  deploy:
    resources:
      limits:
        cpus: 5
        memory: 4G
      reservations:
        cpus: 2
        memory: 1G
  environment:
    - SITE_NAME=${SITE_NAME}
    - DATABASE_HOST=${POSTGRES_SERVER}
    - DATABASE_USER=${POSTGRES_USER}
    - DATABASE_PORT=${POSTGRES_PORT}
    - DATABASE_DBNAME=${POSTGRES_DB}
    - DATABASE_PWD=${POSTGRES_PASSWORD}
    - GEOSERVER_PWD=${GEOSERVER_PASSWORD}
```

The EEW worker can be compute-intensive and is supposed to give quick results. It should be scalable to 1 central processing unit (CPU) per GMM. Memory requirements will depend on the data set size, but more than 1G per GMM should not be required.

3.2.5.2.3 RRE process

```
rre:
  image: ${ECR_URL}/${ECR_STACK_NAME}-bayesian-rre-worker
```

```

entrypoint: ["bayesian_controller"]
deploy:
  resources:
    limits:
      cpus: 8
      memory: 4G
    reservations:
      cpus: 2
      memory: 2G
environment:
  - SITE_NAME=${SITE_NAME}
  - DATABASE_HOST=${POSTGRES_SERVER}
  - DATABASE_USER=${POSTGRES_USER}
  - DATABASE_PORT=${POSTGRES_PORT}
  - DATABASE_DBNAME=${POSTGRES_DB}
  - DATABASE_PWD=${POSTGRES_PASSWORD}
  - GEOSERVER_PWD=${GEOSERVER_PASSWORD}

```

The RRE worker is computationally intensive and is supposed to give quick results. The processing speed depends on the size of dataset and the process can be accelerated to some extent by adding more CPUs. Memory requirements will be around 0.5 to 1GB per CPU.

3.2.5.2.4 OEF Process

```

oef:
  image: ${ECR_URL}/${ECR_STACK_NAME}-hazard-analysis-worker
  build:
    context: .
    dockerfile: docker/hazard_analysis/Dockerfile
  networks:
    - turnkey_backend
    - turnkey_frontend
  entrypoint: ["oef"]
  deploy:
    resources:
      limits:
        cpus: 8
        memory: 8G
      reservations:
        cpus: 2
        memory: 2G
  environment:
    - SITE_NAME=${SITE_NAME}
    - DATABASE_HOST=${POSTGRES_SERVER}
    - DATABASE_USER=${POSTGRES_USER}
    - DATABASE_PORT=${POSTGRES_PORT}
    - DATABASE_DBNAME=${POSTGRES_DB}
    - DATABASE_PWD=${POSTGRES_PASSWORD}
    - GEOSERVER_PWD=${GEOSERVER_PASSWORD}

```

Like the RRE process, the OEF process is computationally intensive and can be made faster by adding CPUs. At least 1 GB should be assigned per process in a normal case.

3.2.5.2.5 Notification process

```
notification:
  image: ${ECR_URL}/${ECR_STACK_NAME}-rest-server
  deploy:
    resources:
      limits:
        cpus: 1
        memory: 500M
      reservations:
        cpus: 0.5
        memory: 250M
  entrypoint: ["notification_listener"]
  environment:
    - SITE_NAME=${SITE_NAME}
    - DATABASE_HOST=${POSTGRES_SERVER}
    - DATABASE_USER=${POSTGRES_USER}
    - DATABASE_PORT=${POSTGRES_PORT}
    - DATABASE_DBNAME=${POSTGRES_DB}
    - DATABASE_PWD=${POSTGRES_PASSWORD}
```

The notification listener has as its main task to wait, query the database and send web requests. Assigned resources can be limited.

3.2.5.2.6 API process

```
rest:
  image: ${ECR_URL}/${ECR_STACK_NAME}-rest-server
  ports:
    - "8081:8080"
  entrypoint: ["swagger_server"]
  deploy:
    resources:
      limits:
        cpus: 1
        memory: 500M
      reservations:
        cpus: 0.5
        memory: 250M
  environment:
    - SITE_NAME=${SITE_NAME}
    - DATABASE_HOST=${POSTGRES_SERVER}
    - DATABASE_USER=${POSTGRES_USER}
    - DATABASE_PORT=${POSTGRES_PORT}
    - DATABASE_DBNAME=${POSTGRES_DB}
    - DATABASE_PWD=${POSTGRES_PASSWORD}
```

The role of the API server is to wait for requests from the GUI and answer those requests. It is not computationally intensive, and not memory intensive. Resources should be around the same as for the notification process.

NOTE: If listening to connections over the internet, a gateway will need to be added on top to secure the connection. See <https://www.docker.com/blog/how-to-use-the-official-nginx-docker-image/> for more information.

3.3 Cloud-based Graphical User Interface Setup

The cloud-based graphical user interface can be used in an as-a-software logic or in a traditional on-premises scenario. In the former case, no installation will be needed while in the latter case the end-users must follow the instruction below.

The installation of the cloud-based GUI should be done using 2 different servers on windows technologies. It's fine to use Virtual Machines. The section provides a step-by-step guidance on the GUI setup. Two databases are needed: one is a Structured Query Language (SQL) Server and the other is a Postgres with GIS extensions. The installation of the basic software is not described in this section.

The user will need the cloud-based GUI to be in communication with the scientific engine (i.e.,g EEW, RRE and OEF engines). These two components need to be on the same network or both exposed over the Internet.

3.3.1 Prerequisites

The users need two Virtual Machine (VM) or Physical Server to have the system installed (hereafter referred as VM1 and VM2). Windows 2019 Essential edition is fine for both VMs. The users will also need a SQL Server and a Postgres DB. For an experimental usage SQL Server Express is fine.

VMs will need to have

- Disk C:\ - 50 GB operating system
- Dick D:\ - 70 GB (this can possibly also be achieved by creating two logical partitions on a single 120 GB disk).

The VMs must have visibility among themselves. The following basic components are per VM:

3.3.1.1 VMI

- The Internet Information Services (IIS) server should be installed with these options as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14 IIS installation options

- SQL Server is reachable. It's fine to install SQL Server in the same VM.
- Microsoft .NET Framework 4.8
- Microsoft .NET Core 3.1

3.3.1.2 VM2

Postgres DB is reachable. It's fine to install Postgres in the same VM.

3.3.2 Installation VM1

The VM1 houses the following artifacts:

- TURNkey management Component
- Service API
 - TURNkey Scientific Engine – Service API
 - TURNkey - Event Creation - Service API
 - TURNkey – Alert Service API
 - Mobile APP Service API 1
 - Mobile APP Service API 2
- GEOS wrapper
- Notify Service

In this installation, the SQL SERVER DB is considered already available on an external environment.

To analyse logs, an access to the SQL Management Studio application is required to be running on this VM.

In the VM1 it must be created, in

- D: \
- the WEB folder, containing these subdirectories
- Emptyroot
 - LOG
 - WrapperGEOS
 - TURNkey

3.3.2.1 TURNkey Management component

A new website called TURNkey that responds on port 80 will be created on IIS, and its application Pool set to NET Common Language Runtime (CLR) version “4.0” and managed Code “integrated”.

The site root will be set to

D: \ WEB \ Turnkey

and the application will be created by creating an application that will point to the path

D: \ WEB \ Turnkey

where the files present in the \ Software \ Sources \ Web directory released on the CD will be added to the site root directory.

3.3.2.2 TURNkey scientific engine - service API

It is the web application that exposes the services allowing the GUI to dialog with the scientific engine and to interact with the user dashboard. It's a .NET Core application.

The site root will be set to:

D: \ WEB \ APIServices

and the application will be implemented by creating an application that will point to the path

D: \ WEB \ APIServices\ApiTurnkey

where the files presented in the \ Software \ Sources \ APIServices \ ApiTurnkey directory released on the CD will be added to the site root directory.

3.3.2.3 TURNkey - Event creation service API

It is the web application that exposes the event services to the other components.

It's a .NET Core application.

The site root will be set to:

D: \ WEB \ APIServices

and the application will be implemented by creating an application that will point to the path:

D: \ WEB \ APIServices\ApiEvent

where the files presented in the \ Software \ Sources \ APIServices \ ApiEvent directory released on the CD will be added to the site root directory.

and the application will be implemented by creating an application that will point to the path

D: \ WEB \ APIServices\ApiOperator

where the files presented in the \ Software \ Sources\ APIServices \ ApiOperator directory released on the CD will be added to the site root directory.

3.3.2.4 TURNkey Alert service API

It is the web application that exposes the alert services to the other components.

It's a .NET Core application.

The site root will be set to:

D: \ WEB \ APIServices

and the application will be implemented by creating an application that will point to the path:

D: \ WEB \ APIServices\ ApiAlert

where the files presented in the \ Software \ Sources\ APIServices \ ApiAlert directory released on the CD will be added to the site root directory.

3.3.2.5 Mobile APP service API 1

It is the web application that exposes the end point services to the mobile app.

It's a .NET Framework application.

The site root will be set to:

D: \ WEB \ Emptyroot

and the application will be implemented by creating an application that will point to the path:

D: \ WEB \ Emptyroot \ APPApi

where the files presented in the \ Software \ Sources\ APIServices \ APPApi directory released on the CD will be added to the site root directory.

3.3.2.6 Mobile App service API 2

It is the web application that exposes the mobile services app devoted to the operator (position location and observation)

It's a .NET Core application.

The site root will be set to:

D: \ WEB \ APIServices

3.3.2.7 Wrapper component

A new website will be created on IIS called WrapperGeos that responds on port 82, and its application Pool set to "no managed code" and managed Code "integrated".

The site root will be set to:

D: \ WEB \ Emptyroot

and the application will be implemented by creating an application that will point to the path

D: \ WEB \ WrapperGEOS

where the files presented in the \ Software \ Sources \ Wrapper directory released on the CD will be added to the site root directory.

3.3.2.8 Notify Service component

The CheckNotifications application will be installed as a windows service or using the NET START command.

Copy the files from the directory \ Software \ Sources \ CheckNotifications released on the Apache Subversion (SVN) server and save them in an easily accessible local directory. The installation command must be run only after configuring the application to access the Clever notify database and services.

3.3.3 Installation VM2

The VM dedicated to the geographic component (VM2) must host the following application components:

- Web component of the Geographic Module
- API component for integration of the Geographic Module with the Management Module

As already highlighted in the prerequisites, the VM should have the 50 GB disk C: \ and the 70 GB disk D: \, by logical division (or by making two partitions on a single 120 GB disk). Prerequisite is that the network settings allow internet browsing.

For product management and verification, the Chrome browser should be installed locally: to do this, copy the package from the \ Software \ Sources \ GEOS \ Prerequisites folder on the CD:

- ChromeSetup.exe

The Visual C ++ 2015-2019 and Java libraries must also be installed: download from the \ Software \ Sources \ GEOS \ Prerequisites folder on the CD and run the following packages:

- VC_redist.x64.exe (version 14.25)
- VC_redist.x86.exe (version 14.25)
- Jre-8u251-windows-x64.exe *

Set the JAVA_HOME variable pointing to the Java installation folder (ex: C: \ Program Files \ Java \ jre1.8.0_251)

(* alternatively download Java from <https://www.oracle.com/it/java/technologies/javase-jre8-downloads.html>, downloading the 64-bit version for Windows)

Finally, for ease of procedure in the implementation of the product:

Copy from \ Software \ Sources \ GEOS \ Components the folder GEOS2 (SVN) in D: \ GEOS2 (containing the WEB site)

In this installation, the Postgres DB is considered already available on an external environment. The requirements of the Postgres DB are indicated in the Postgres component paragraph

The steps to follow for installation are indicated below.

3.3.3.1 Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP)

The link to download the binaries <https://windows.php.net/download>

1. Copy \ Software \ Sources \ GEOS \ Components the php (CD) folder to d: \ php
2. Add the path d: \ php to the system path variable.

Alternatively, it is possible (paying attention to the versions and related prerequisites):

3. Download the php binaries (version 7.2.5.0) from <https://windows.php.net/download>
4. Create the d: \ php folder and copy the binaries into it

5. Add the path "d: \ php \" to the system paths
6. Edit the D: \ php \ php.ini file and check the correspondence of the extension path:
7. extension_dir = "D: \ php \ ext"

Note: In case of deployment in different paths, edit the PHPIniDir variable

3.3.3.2 Apache

To install and configure Apache24, proceed as follows:

1. Copy the entire Apache24 folder from \ Software \ Sources \ GEOS \ Components to CD and copy it to D: \ Apache24. The package contains the version 2.4.33 of Apache with the appropriate configurations already present.
2. Finally, install it as a service: open a command prompt and go to the D: \ Apache24 \ bin folder and run the command: httpd -k install

Alternatively, it is possible (paying attention to the versions and related prerequisites):

1. Download the binaries from <https://www.apachelounge.com/download/> and copy them to D: \ Apache24
2. Edit the file D: \ Apache24 \ conf \ httpd.conf and verify that the section is present:
LoadModule php7_module "d: /php/php7apache2_4.dll"
· PHPIniDir "d: / php"
AddHandler application / x-httpd-php .php

Note: In case of deployment in different paths, edit the PHPIniDir variable

3. To install it as a service, from the \ bin folder run the command: httpd -k install
4. Edit the file: D: \ Apache24 \ conf \ httpd.conf and set:
DocumentRoot "D: / GEOS2"
<Directory "D: / GEOS2">
Options FollowSymLinks
AllowOverride None
Require all granted
</Directory>

3.3.3.3 Node.js

Copy the file node-v14.16.0-x64.msi to the desired location from \ Software \ Sources \ GEOS \ Components on CD

Run node-v14.16.0-x64.msi and install with the default parameters

Alternatively, the user can download the Nodejs binaries from: <https://nodejs.org/en/download/> and proceed with the installation as described above, leaving all the default parameters.

3.3.3.4 Postgres component

The Postgres engine is not in this VM. However, some actions, in particular the possible recompilation of the API and the management of the DB, require the presence of the libraries libpq and a management interface: for this it is necessary to install PgAdmin 4, which can be downloaded at <https://www.pgadmin.org/download/pgadmin-4-windows/>.

Please check that a Postgres is installed on the user's network (prerequisite) and that the Postgis extension is installed.

In the PostgreSQL installation it must be specified to implement the geospatial data abstraction library (GDAL) and the variable GDAL_DATA must be specified in the system variables (making it point for example to C:\Program Files\PostgreSQL\12\gdal-data)

Note: the solution uses PostgreSQL at least version 12.2.4 64-bit with Postgis

Proceed as follows:

For ease of management, if available, the user can use the PgAdmin tool:

- Create a database named GEOS2
- Attach the "postgis" extension to the GEOS2 DB (e.g., through PgAdmin select the GEOS2 database, then select extensions, right click -> create -> extension and select postgis)
- Create geos user, with db_owner role on the GEOS2 database: via Pgadmin or:
- CREATE USER geos WITH PASSWORD 'xxxx'; (password chosen at will)
- (Be sure to give him the ability to login to the DB)
- Restore the DB GEOS2.sql dump taken from \Software\Sources\GEOS\DBGEOS SVN in the "DBGEOS" folder

Note: This "geos" user and relative password must be specified in the configuration files, as indicated below.

For monitoring, it will also be appropriate to create a special read-only user:

- CREATE USER mon WITH PASSWORD 'xxxx'; (with password chosen at will)
- Give user privileges (grant also to tables) for viewing
- (Be sure to provide them with the ability to login to the DB)

3.3.3.5 Geoviewer

3.3.3.5.1 Web Component

1. Copy the web_config folder from \Software\Sources\GEOS\SVN Components and copy it to D:\web_config
2. Download the GEOS2 folder from \Software\Sources\GEOS\SVN Components and copy it to D:\GEOS2 (if not already done as previously indicated in the chapter dedicated to the prerequisites)
3. Make sure that the following files are present in the GEOS2 folder (for connection to the DB):
 - D:\GEOS2\GEOS\db_connection.php
 - D:\GEOS2\webserver\models\Geos2\database.ini

The configuration will be described in the chapter dedicated to configuration.

4. For each Agency and Customer, the file must exist:
D:\web_config\GEOS2_(agency)_(customer).conf

For simplicity, the GEOS2_Customer_Turnkey.conf file is already provided: the configuration will be described in the chapter dedicated to configuration.

5. The GEOS execution link is:

[http://localhost/geos/index.php?agency=XXX & customer=XXX & user=test](http://localhost/geos/index.php?agency=XXX&customer=XXX&user=test)

In this phase the maps will not load correctly since the configuration part has not been completed.

6. Copy icons: copy icons from CD\Software\Sources\GEOS\Components\GEOS2\GEOS\icons. To allow any subsequent updates of icons, set up an FTP service on the Cartographic VM, with

software of user choice for the transmission and updating of the icons in D:\GEOS2\GEOS\icons, and make sure that communication from the VM1 is possible.

3.3.3.5.2 API Component

To proceed with the compilation of the API modules, the user must first install the Python 2.7 and the Visual C++ build tools, and then recompile the API modules based on the version of Nodejs installed:

1. Make sure that the \api subfolder exists in D:\GEOS2
2. Make sure that the setting.js file is present in the section relating to access to the PostgreSQL database, the configuration will take place in the next step.
3. Open a command prompt, navigate to the d:\GEOS2\api folder and run the commands:
 - npm install --global --production windows-build-tools
4. (Wait patiently for the installation to finish without closing the prompt, just send when Python 2.7 installed appears)
 - npm install

At this point the modules will have been recompiled, and it will be possible to carry out the tests.

Note: the user can start the API in test via command from the \api folder with the command: node server.js, the console must indicate that the server has started and shows the list of exposed ports, as shown in Figure 15.

```
D:\GEOS2>cd api
D:\GEOS2\api>node server.js
15:05:17 -> Server is starting in ENVIRONMENT: official
15:05:17 -> This process is your pid 10200
15:05:17 -> CAD Server EndPoint: http://localhost/webserver/cad.php
15:05:17 -> Connecting on localhost:5432 with user: postgres and db: geos2
15:05:17 -> Connected!
15:05:17 -> WebSocket Server enabled over HTTP
15:05:17 -> API Server enabled over HTTP
15:05:17 -> REST API Server Started on port: 9600
15:05:17 -> API Server enabled over HTTP
15:05:17 -> REST MAP Server Started on port: 9601
15:05:17 -> API Server enabled over HTTP
15:05:17 -> REST OSRM Server Started on port: 9602
15:05:17 -> API Server enabled over HTTP
15:05:17 -> REST VIARIO Server Started on port: 9603
15:05:17 -> WebSocket Server is listening on port: 8123
```

Figure 15 Compilation of the API module

Now the user can install Nodejs as a windows service:

- Copy \Software\Sources\GEOS\SVN Components the NSSM directory to D:\NSSM
- Open a command prompt and go to the d:\NSSM directory and issue the command:

NSSM install API
- Set the parameters as shown in Figure 16:

Figure 16 Parameters for the installation of Nodejs

- From Windows Services console start the Geos_API service that has been just created.

3.3.4 Installation of the TURNkey Database SQL Server

Proceed in the following way:

- Import the file Emma2_CM.bacpac using the tool “Import Data-tier Application” of SQL server Management Studio
- Rename the database in Emma2_CM
- Import the file GENSEC_MULTI.bacpac using the tool “Import Data-tier Application” di SQL server Management Studio
- Rename the imported database in GENSEC_MULTI

The database will not contain any data except the first user:

- **SYSADM** super administrator

The default password is “changeoninstall”. It’s important to remember to change password.

The SYSADM user has the power to configure which features can be used by users. Changing the list of features impacts the operation of the system. Improper use of the capabilities of the SYSADM user could make the TURNkey system unusable from a functional point of view. For this reason, it is recommended to follow the indications given in this section.

3.3.5 Configuration

3.3.5.1 TURNkey Management component

Within the installation directory of the TURNkey Management application, open the web.config file with notepad and modify the following parts:

1. **ConnectionStrings**: replace the values of the connection string named CMEntities with the respective access values of the EMMA_CM database installed in the SQL Cluster SERVER and replace the values of the connection string called GenSec2Context with the respective access values of the GENSEC_MULTI database installed in the SQL Cluster SERVER.

2. **Beta80.Emma2.CM.Integrations.Clevernotify.CM.Service.Properties.Settings:** replace the values of the gatewayAddress, gatewayUser, gatewayPassword and Title parameters with the values necessary for using the Clever Notify API.

Then, start the application from a browser and log in using the SYSADM account. Access the "System" menu and click on the "System settings" item.

Table 8 presents the interface path to follow and the list of parameters to be changed.

Table 8 The interface path for system setting. The user writes in step 3 the parameters to be changed

Table 9 shows the parameter that need to be configured.

Table 9 Parameters to be configured

Parameter	New Value
Geos.CartographicUrl	e.g., <code>http://xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx/GEOS/index.php?</code>
Geos.Wrapper.BaseURL	e.g., <code>http://xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx/WrapperGEOS</code>
System.ApplicationBaseUrl	e.g., <code>http://xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx/GEST/</code>

Note: the wrapper uniform resource locator (URL) will be without the final slash, while the management software URL will be with the slash.

3.3.5.2 Wrapper Geos

Within the publication directory of the Wrapper application, create the following directory tree under the Configurations directory:

... / Configurations / *CustomerName*¹ / Turnkey

Finally, in the TURNkey directory, create the "Beta80.iO.GIS.GEOS2.json" file containing the following information:

```
{
  "GeocodeUrl": "http://xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx:3004",
  "PathUrl": "http://xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx:9602",
  "ResourceUrl": "http://xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx:9600",
  "MapUrl": "http://xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx:9601",
  "PushUrl": "http://xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx/Safety1St/api/PushDrawGeo",
}
```

Where the first 4 items will contain the IP address or DNS associated with the geographic VM (VM2), while item 5 will contain the IP address or DNS associated with the TURNkey VM (VM1).

3.3.5.3 Notify Service – Configuration

In the local directory where the files taken from the released \ Software \ Sources \ CheckNotifications folder of the CD downloaded, open the Beta80.Emma2.CM.WindowsService.CheckNotifications.exe.config file with notepad and modify the following parts:

3. ConnectionStrings: replace the values of the connection string named CMEntities with the respective access values of the EMMA_CM database installed in the SQL SERVER Cluster.

4. Beta80.Emma2.CM.Integrations.Clevertify.CM.Service.Properties.Settings: replace the values of the gatewayAddress, gatewayUser, gatewayPassword and Title parameters with the values necessary for using the Clever Notify API.

3.3.5.4 Geoviewer – Configuration

3.3.5.4.1 Database

The first step is to configure the access of the geographic component to the Database, it is therefore necessary to configure the access to the PostgreSQL database in the following files:

- D:\GEOS2\GEOS\db_connection.php

¹ The Name of the Customers (for instance Alicante)

// Connecting, selecting database

```
$db_host="xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx";           (ip or dns del db Postgres)
$db_port="5432";                       (port db Postgres)
$db_name="GEOS2";                       (name db Postgres)
$db_user="geos";                         (user geos with full power on the DB)
$db_password="xxx";                     (select by the user)
```

- D:\GEOS2\webserver\models\Geos2\database.ini
; Official Env
host_official=xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx (ip o dns del DB Postgres)
port_official=5432 (port DB Postgres)
database_official=GEOS2 (name DB Postgres)
user_official=geos (user geos con poteri full sul db)
password_official=xxx (select by the user)

For access to the Database (API component):

- Configure the setting.js file in the section relating to access to the PostgreSQL database, by entering the credentials of the user configured for access to the GEOS2 database.
- Configure the D: \ GEOS2 \ api \ setting.js file in the section relating to access to the PostgreSQL database, by entering the credentials of the "geos" user configured for access to the GEOS2 database.

```
DB_URL: "xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx"           (ip o dns DB Postgres)
DB_PORT : "5432"                     (port DB Postgres)
DB_USER : "geos"                     (user geos with full power on the DB)
DB_PASSWORD: "xxx"                   (select by the user)
DB_NAME : "GEOS2"                     (name for the DB: it's case sensitive!)
```

3.3.5.4.2 Configuration file

Once the previous steps have been completed, it is necessary to proceed with the configuration of the Agency and Customer. The Turnkey Management Module sends the resources to be displayed on the map through the GIS Wrapper, each resource is saved in the GEOS2 PostgreSQL database in the "geos_resources" table.

GEOS2 shows them on the screen by applying the styles defined in the "geos_configuration" table or by directly using those contained in each single resource.

The configuration relating to the agency_code and customer_code equal to "****" is to be considered by default, the GEOS2 loads it if it does not find the specific configuration on an agency / customer basis passed in POST in the execution link.

For each agency and customer, it is necessary, starting from the basic file GEOS2.conf, to create the file d: \ web_config \ GEOS2_agency_customer.conf (eg. GEOS2_Veneto_Safety1st.conf - already provided in d: \ web_config)

It is possible to test the correct loading of the GEOS configuration without going through the Turnket Management, simply pass the Agency & Customer & User parameters (the user is optional) directly in the link, for example:

`http://localhost/GEOS/index.php? agency = Alicante & customer = Turnkey & user = APP`

The configuration is done partly on the database and partly on the configuration file in `d:\web_config`

To configure, proceed as follows:

- Access the GEOS2 database
- Access the "geos_configurations" table
- For the agency_code (e.g., "ALICANTE") and customer_code (e.g., "Turnkey") the following records must exist, as shown in Table 10:

Table 10 The necessary records for agency_code and customer_code

Attribute	Value
base_layers	"Earthquake", "Rescuers", "Infrastructure", "GeoArea", "Territorial Presence", "Custom draw"
start center	11.747194,45.464201 (where the map s centered)
Start zoom	12
Default_style	Default styles (this is precompiled)

In the GEOS2_agency_customer file, the "Layer GEOS2_config" section must be entered where for each "Resource_Type" (point 1) there must be an entry where feattyp = resource_type. By setting to true or false, the user can deactivate the layers: it is important, however, that they correspond to those present in the DB.

Here is an example:

```
var GEOS2_config = [
  {name: "Earthquake", feattyp:"EVENTS", enabled:true,onstart:true, LZ: 1, MZ:16, HZ:18},
  {name: "Rescuers", feattyp:"VOLUNTEERS", enabled:false,onstart:true, LZ: 14, MZ:16, HZ:18},
  {name: "Infrastrutture", feattyp:"INFRASTRUCTURES", enabled:false,onstart:true, LZ: 14, MZ:16, HZ:18},
  {name: "Presidi territoriali", feattyp:"TER_PRESENCES", enabled:true,onstart:true, LZ: 14, MZ:16, HZ:18},
  {name: "Segnalazioni", feattyp:"SIGNALINGS", enabled:true,onstart:true, LZ: 14, MZ:16, HZ:18},
  {name: "Aree di rischio", feattyp:"RISK_AREAS", enabled:true,onstart:true, LZ: 14, MZ:16, HZ:18},
  {name: "Superfici strategiche", feattyp:"STRATEGIC_SURFACES", enabled:true,onstart:true, LZ: 14, MZ:16, HZ:18},
  {name: "Custom Draw", feattyp:"CUSTOM_DRAW", enabled:true,onstart:true, LZ: 14, MZ:16, HZ:18}];
```

Check if the result is as expected by clicking on the appropriate icon. The configuration in fact determines the menu of management resources, as shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17 Check configuration

3.3.5.4.3 Google Licence Activation

- In the configuration file `d:\web_config\GEOS2.conf` and `GEOS2_Agency_Customer.conf` used, enter the specific key for the customer to enable the Google API. The following is an example key:
- `var EBW_apikey = "AIzaSyD0QWRISTr3fD0qErbHMsAZ-G5y3R6PIIM";`

The key, similar to the one in the example, is unique and must be generated by Beta 80 after the publication of the Geos. In this phase it is therefore necessary to coordinate with Beta 80.

- in the file `D:\GEOS2\GEOS\assets\scripts\libs\ebw\ebw_baselayer.js` make sure that the part in bold is present, or add at the end of the italicized part:

```
var url = "";
if (typeof EBW_channel === 'undefined')
    url = "https://maps.googleapis.com/maps/api/js?v=3&libraries=places&callback=GoogleMapApiLoaded";
else
    url = "https://maps.googleapis.com/maps/api/js?v=3.31&libraries=places&callback=GoogleMapApiLoaded&client=gme-ebworldsrl&channel=beta80.geos."+EBW_channel;

// NEW KEY MANAGEMENT MODE
if (typeof EBW_apikey! === 'undefined' && EBW_apikey! === "")
    url = "https://maps.googleapis.com/maps/api/js?v=3.31&libraries=places&callback=GoogleMapApiLoaded&key="+EBW_apikey;
```

3.3.5.4.4 WMS

Here are the steps necessary to configure a vector map service having a WMS service as a source. The endpoints of the WMS services are consumed on the client side, this means that the client (browser) must be able to reach them.

- Enable the WMS menu. Put a true the option “enabled”

```
{
  'label' : 'Cartografie',
  'action' : 'wms',
  'enabled': true,
  'content': WMS_overlays_config
},
```

The user can personalize the menu display label, as shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18 Personalisation of the menu display label

Configure the WMS

A server must be defined for each source, the URL depends on the service, sometimes ends with / wms. The geos doesn't even support basic authentication.

```
var WMS_server={"server1": {url:"http://t1.openseamap.org"},
  "server2": {url:"http://..."},
  "server3": {url:"http://..."}
};
```

- After defining the server, the layers exposed by the service must be defined. The “feattyp” is a value ranging from L1 to L (n), they must be unique. The name is what appears in the WMS menu.

```
var WMS_overlays_config = [
  {server: "server1",feattyp:"L1", type: "xyz", format:"seamark/{z}/{x}/{y}.png",
  name:"OpenSeaMap", enabled:true},
  {server: "server2",feattyp:"L2", type: "xyz", format:"XXX ", name:"Layername1",
  enabled:true},
  {server: "server2",feattyp:"L3", type: "xyz", format:"XX ", name:"Layername2",
  enabled:true},
  {server: "server3",feattyp:"L4", type: "xyz", format:"XXX", name:"Layername3",
  enabled:true},
  {server: "server3",feattyp:"L(n)", type: "xyz", format:"XXX", name:"Layername(n)",
  enabled:true}
];
```

3.3.5.5 Configuration checklist

Table 11 shows the checklist that the user should do to verify that the installation has been performed properly.

Table 11 Cloud-based graphical user interface installation checklist

ID	Objectives	Function to test	Profile	Results
1	Log in to the platform	Verify that the home page appears		<p>A login page is presented to the user</p>
2	First authentication	Use the credential that have been set-up for the user VADM	VADM	<p>The user will have access to a page like that</p> <p>The home page may be look different according to the setting.</p>
3	Open the Geoviewer	<p>Click on the map icon</p>		
4-1	Verify the communication between the Turnkey Application and the Geoviewer	<p>Click on new “Earthquake”</p>		
4-2		<p>Use the tool. Click on “start”</p> <p>① and ② draw point</p>		

4-3		<p>Press the button save on the tool</p>		
5	<p>Verify that the notification system is properly installed</p>	<p>From the login form ask to change password.</p>	<p>VADM</p>	<p>The password change will appear.</p>

4 PLATFORM UP-RUNNING: SYNTHETIC ICELANDOPOLIS

4.1 General characteristics of the Iceland testbed

Iceland is the most seismically active region in northern Europe. The Icelandic Hot Spot, a localized column of magmatic upwelling from the mantle, drives the volcanism and seismicity of Iceland as it interacts with the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, a plate margin of active tectonic extension that runs along the entire length of the Atlantic Ocean. The towns of Hveragerði, south Iceland, and Húsavík, north Iceland constitute Testbed 3 Iceland (TB3). Hveragerði is located near the triple-junction of the South Iceland Seismic Zone (SISZ), Reykjanes Peninsula Oblique Rift (RPOR) zone, and the Western Volcanic Zone, while Húsavík is located near the Tjörnes Fracture Zone (TFZ), sitting directly on top of the largest transform fault in Iceland. The SISZ-RPOR and TFZ are the two largest transform zones in Iceland and historically the most damaging earthquakes occur in these zones.

For demonstration purposes, synthetic data populated or modified based on the actual data is used (e.g., exposure data, V_{S30} map). The synthetic testbed is named Icelandopolis.

4.2 Platform installation and setting up

Please see section 3.2 for more information. Dataset to install will be provided on request.

4.2.1 Configuration and setting up of the local seismic networks

The TURNkey sensor setup in the Icelandic testbed (TB3) comprises 50 TURNkey multisensor RS4D, 6 of which are collocated with TURNkey GNSS sensors. The station deployment consists of rural regional and urban local free-field ground-motion monitoring sites, and structural health monitoring. In addition, selected existing sensors in TB3 are being incorporated into the TURNkey system, primarily from stations of the existing strong-motion arrays in the TB along with key stations of the national network with the purpose of contributing to OEF and EEW.

4.2.2 Real-time seismic data transmission from networks to the platform

The datacentre of TB3 is operated by UICE/IMO. It operates a full SeisComp EEW system. The seismic and GNSS data are acquired locally on the RS4D and sent to the CAPS system operated by UICE. From there the seismic and GNSS data is forwarded to the CAPS system of the TURNkey platform. The protocol from instrumentation to real-time data streaming to local servers, and data streaming to the central Phobos system of GMP has been verified and validated. The integration of the GNSS data streams is yet to be completed and, as planned, the new TURNkey RS4D firmware is deployed.

Examples of real-time seismic data transmission from networks to the platform are given in section 4.3.

4.2.3 Setup of the scientific engines

4.2.3.1 Parameters

For the parameter setup for Icelandopolis please refer to Chapter 3.

4.2.3.2 Hazard data

4.2.3.2.1 Seismic zonation map

A seismic zonation model is useful for risk mitigation purposes such as the implementation of earthquake-resistant design of structures, risk analysis, land-use planning, and other applications. The seismic zonation model must contain information about the a -value and b -value of the Gutenberg–Richter relation while it can optionally contain information of the maximum magnitudes and hypocentral depths. This data can be prepared by earthquake engineers or seismologists who perform national or regional seismic hazard analyses.

The Iceland-specific seismic hazard is shown in Figure 19 and was provided by the UIce. If a country-specific seismic zonation map is not available, the scientific engine will use the 2013 Euro-Mediterranean Seismic Hazard Model (ESHM13) (Giardini, et al., 2013), including a classic Area Source (AS) Model and a kernel-smoothed model that generates earthquake rate forecasts based on fault slip and smoothed seismicity (SEIFA). It is worth noting that ESHM13 is currently being updated by the European Seismic Hazard Model 2020 (ESHM20) (Crowley, et al., 2020) and the default hazard data on the platform will be updated once the source data are released.

Figure 19. Iceland seismic zonation maps from UIce

4.2.3.2.2 V_{S30} data

The V_{S30} (the time-averaged shear-wave velocity to 30 m depth) data are used to classify ground types in Eurocode 8 (CEN, 2005), which is then used to account for the influence of local ground conditions on the seismic action. V_{S30} is also used in the international standards (e.g., ASCE, 2022) for site classification and used as a proxy for site amplification in ground motion prediction models (Lanzano, et al., 2019).

The end-user can prepare region-specific V_{S30} data based on the geotechnical soil investigations, laboratory tests, estimates based on a topographic slope, or other proxies. By default, the scientific engine utilizes the USGS V_{S30} models and data (Heath, et al., 2020, <https://earthquake.usgs.gov/data/vs30/>).

For the synthetic Icelandopolis region, the V_{S30} is modified based on the USGS V_{S30} to manually create areas with soft sediment and very hard rock, as shown in Figure 20.

4.2.3.3 Exposure data

The exposure of people and properties to earthquake risk is a key component in seismic risk estimation. A synthetic Icelandopolis dataset in the area of interest is used to illustrate the possible range of properties, as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 20. The synthetic V_{S30} map for the Icelandopolis region

Figure 21. Synthetic Icelandopolis exposure data: geoareas: black line; general buildings: orange circle; CISs: blue diamond; EFs: red cross

4.2.3.4 Vulnerability data

To assess the physical and social vulnerabilities of the area of interest, the scientific engine includes libraries of fragility functions, capacity functions, vulnerability functions, damage-to-loss functions and functionality functions. By default, each building typology or each type of the critical infrastructure system has two equally-weighted fragility functions. The end-user can assign up to five suitable fragility functions with weights to any building typology or any type of critical infrastructure system.

4.3 Real-time simulation

A real-time simulation is to demonstrate the daily operation of the TURNkey platform. The scenario of interest is a mainshock that occurs within the study area followed by a series of aftershocks and the platform will provide the real-time shake map and risk and loss estimation to facilitate emergency response, taking into account the instrumental data, DYFI reports and eyewitness reports. It is worth noting that the example shown in this section is for demonstration only. To have a realistic estimation of the seismic hazard for the end-users, the input data/parameters should be carefully selected/tuned based on site-specific seismological and engineering considerations.

4.3.1 EEW

The EEW alert of events (for both mainshock and aftershocks) will appear on the TURNkey platform if the scientific engine sends out a relevant notification, as shown in Figure 22. Moreover, the EEW alert for aftershock will be available in the mobile application. The end-user can check the most affected area to have a first estimate of the earthquake impact, as shown in Figure 23.

Figure 22 Left: the EEW alert on the platform. Right: the EEW alert for aftershock in the mobile application.

Figure 23. The most affected region covering the area with estimated PGA \geq pre-defined threshold in %

For an earthquake with a potential damaging impact, shake maps of PGA and macroseismic intensity will be quickly generated, as shown in Figure 24 and Figure 25. It is worth noting that the presented example is based on synthetic dataset. The high ground shakings presented in Figure 24 and Figure 25 are due to the high GMM estimates for soil sites. The selected GMMs use two-category site classification (i.e., rock with $V_{S30} \geq 800$ m/s and soil with $V_{S30} < 800$ m/s) and a site amplification factor around 2.3 for soil site is considered in the selected GMMs.

Figure 24. The PGA shake map in g. The synthetic case study is for demonstration only. The high ground shaking estimates are due to high GMM estimates for soil sites.

Figure 25. The EMS-98 intensity shake map. The synthetic case study is for demonstration only. The high ground shaking estimates are due to high GMM estimates for soil sites.

Following the predefined procedure by the end-user, the GUI sent out information to the target users/groups, as shown in Figure 26. Moreover, the GUI is connected to the widely used social media platforms (e.g., Twitter, Facebook) and the user can send out messages to the public through the GUI (under the user's account), as shown in Figure 27. The risk-mitigation measures defined in the protocols are automatically triggered as shown in Figure 28.

Figure 26. Communication between the GUI and end-user.

Figure 27. Communication between the GUI and the public.

Figure 28. Threshold-based risk-mitigation measures automatically triggered.

4.3.2 RRE

With the streaming instrumental data and smart-phone data, the shake maps of PGA and macroseismic intensity are regularly updated. As shown in Figure 29, four instrumental PGA values are sent to the scientific engine to update the shake maps.

Figure 29. Four instrumental PGA (circle sized by PGA values in %g) are used to update the shake map. The epicentre of the mainshock is denoted by the star.

Given the observations and spatial correlation, the shake maps of PGA and macroseismic intensity are updated, as shown in Figure 30 and Figure 31. Compared to the EEW shake map in Figure 24 and Figure 25, the reliability of the updated RRE shake maps is significantly improved after taking into account the real-time eyewitness observations and spatial correlation. It is worth noting that the presented example is for demonstration only. The site classification in the RRE process considers eight categories with different site amplification factors, which provides higher resolution than those GMMs with simplified site classification. The high ground shakings presented in Figure 30 and Figure 31 are due to the high GMM estimates for soil sites, the synthetic observations and strong spatial correlation.

For the general buildings, the damage estimates can be checked under the “Impacted Geo Areas” tag as a map, where the colour is defined based on the average mean damage ratio, as shown in Figure 32. Moreover, the results can also be shown as a table, where the average damage state over the geoarea is colour-coded (green-yellow-red corresponds to no damage-partially damaged-damaged states, respectively), as shown in Figure 33. Detailed information of the physical and social vulnerabilities for each geoarea is presented as a pie chart, as shown in Figure 34.

Figure 30. The updated PGA shake map in g. The high ground shaking estimates are due to 1) high GMM estimates for soil sites; 2) synthetic observations; 3) strong spatial correlation.

Figure 31. The updated EMS-98 intensity shake map. The high ground shaking estimates are due to 1) high GMM estimates for soil sites; 2) synthetic observations; 3) strong spatial correlation.

Figure 32. The map of average damage estimates for general buildings / geosarea

Figure 33. The general risk and loss estimation table for general buildings / geosarea

Figure 34. The detailed risk and loss estimation results for general buildings / geoarea

For EFs and CISs, the risk and loss estimation can be presented in the map view as shown in Figure 35, and a summary table of the physical and social vulnerabilities is shown when clicking the property of interest. Moreover, the risk and loss results can also be checked under the “Impacted Infrastructure” tag as a table, where the property-specific damage state is colour-coded in the same way as those for the general building/geoarea.

Figure 35 The map view of EFs and CISs risk and loss results. There is no damage to “the FUTURE airport control tower”.

Figure 36 The general risk and loss estimation table for Efs and CISs

Figure 37. The detailed risk and loss estimation results for EFs and CISs

The user can submit eyewitness reports through either the platform or the TURNkey app, as shown in Figure 38 and Figure 39.

The screenshot shows the 'NEW OBSERVATION' form on the TURNkey platform. The form is divided into two main sections: 'GENERAL INFORMATION' and 'OTHER DATA'. In the 'GENERAL INFORMATION' section, there is a 'Description' text field, an 'Event' dropdown menu with coordinates 'E22TB300079 - 63° 55' 39.31" N - 20° 42' 45.64" W', and three dropdown menus for 'Infrastructure category' (Transportatin), 'Category' (Airport Transportation System), and 'Infrastructure' (FUTURE Airport Control Tower). The 'OTHER DATA' section includes 'Damage state' (DS1: Minor damage), 'Functionality loss (%)' (2), 'Death number' (1), 'Homeless number' (4), and 'Shelter number' (2). The interface includes a top navigation bar with the user name 'Vezzoso Alberto', a language dropdown set to 'English', and a 'TURNkey' logo. A left sidebar contains various navigation icons. 'Delete' and 'Save' buttons are located at the top right of the form area.

Figure 38. Submit eyewitness report on the TURNkey platform

The screenshot displays the TURNkey mobile app interface for submitting an eyewitness report. The screen is titled 'Observations' and is divided into four main panels: 'Overview', 'Status', 'Photo', and 'Summary'. The 'Overview' panel shows the event details: 'EARTHQUAKES: Earthquake 2/3/2022 12:44:03 PM (created by the engine) E22TB300093' and 'ASSET: FUTURE Airport Parking Structure Icendapolis (Icendapolis)'. The 'DESCRIPTION' field contains the text 'Test'. The 'Status' panel shows 'DAMAGE LEVEL: DS 2: Moderate damage', 'FUNCTIONALITY LOSS: 60%' with a progress bar, and input fields for 'Number of persons impacted' (4), 'Number of homeless persons', and 'Number of shelters needed'. The 'Photo' panel shows a photo of a building. The 'Summary' panel provides a concise overview of the report: 'EARTHQUAKES: Earthquake 2/3/2022 12:44:03 PM (created by the engine)', 'INFRASTRUCTURE: Icendapolis (Icendapolis)', 'DESCRIPTION: Test', 'DAMAGE LEVEL: DS 2: Moderate damage', 'FUNCTIONALITY LOSS: 60.0%', 'PHOTO: 1', and 'NUMBER OF PERSONS IMPACTED: 4'. At the bottom, there are navigation arrows for 'STATUS', 'OVERVIEW', 'PHOTO', 'SUMMARY', and 'PHOTO'. A camera icon is visible in the bottom right corner.

Figure 39. Submit eyewitness report on the TURNkey app

Given the observations for general buildings / geoarea, the corresponding average mean damage ratio is updated as shown in Figure 40. Given the observations at the building location, the risk and loss estimations are updated accordingly as shown in Figure 41.

Figure 40. The updated map of average damage estimates for general buildings / geoaera

Figure 41. The updated map view of EFs and CISOs risk and loss results. The “FUTURE high school” is observed to be partially damaged.

The communications between the GUI and the end-user, between the end-user and the relevant organizations/personnel, between the end-users and the public, are the same as that in the EEW process.

4.3.3 OEF

The OEF first requests the recent earthquake catalogue (a strong mainshock-aftershock sequence in Figure 42) to estimate the short-term seismic hazard. As shown in Figure 43, the estimated daily probability of exceeding PGA level 0.005g based on the background and time-dependent seismicity data presented on the platform. The increased probability of strong shaking in the area of interest is computed based on these two maps. For comparison purposes, the OEF results based on a weak mainshock-aftershock sequence are also presented in Figure 44.

Figure 42. The event catalogue between 2021-02-24 00:00:00 and 2021-02-25 00:00:00 observed by the TURNkey instrumental network

Figure 43. The OEF seismic hazard results given a strong mainshock-aftershock sequence (in Figure 42)

Figure 44. The OEF seismic hazard results given a weak mainshock-aftershock sequence.

4.4 Event simulation

On the TURNkey platform, the user can simulate the earthquake scenario of interest by specifying the location, magnitude, and hypocentre depth, as shown in Figure 45. The same results as those in the RRE process will be presented in the dashboard.

Figure 45. Event simulation

The user can always check the static vulnerability level information for geoarea or for EFs and CISs, which helps identify the most vulnerable area of interest, as shown in Figure 46.

Figure 46. The distribution of the vulnerability levels in geosareas.

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